
Master Thesis
Topology Optimization
of 3D Photonic Band Gap Crystals

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Preface

This master thesis has been written at the Department of Mechanical Engineering (MEK), Solid Mechanics (FAM), at the Technical University of Denmark (DTU), under the supervision of Professor, Dr. Techn. Ole Sigmund and Assistant Professor, Ph.D. Allan Roulund Gersborg. The thesis constitutes the final part of the requirements for obtaining the Danish Master of Science degree (Cand. Polyt.). The project is credited with 30 ECTS points and the work has been carried out from August 1st 2007 to December 31st 2007.

It is assumed that the reader has basic knowledge within the fields of nodal based finite elements and mathematics.

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Abstract

Three dimensional photonic band gap crystals are a class of engineered materials with the ability to prevent propagation of electromagnetic waves with arbitrary polarization within a certain frequency range. This thesis describes the application of the topology optimization method to the design problem of determining optimized geometries of 3D photonic crystals with large band gaps. Though present fabrication techniques cannot realize fully 3D photonic crystals in the visible spectrum of light, the potential applications are many, and promise tremendous advances in e.g. the fields of telecommunication as perfect waveguides and super computing as light based transistors. The objective of this thesis is thus to formulate and implement an optimization problem, which can be used to design 3D infinitely periodic photonic crystals, and if possible, to investigate simplified designs based on these findings.

The basic physics governing photonic crystals is presented in the form of Maxwell's vectorial equations. These equations are rewritten on timeharmonic form and includes the Bloch wave representation. The concept of the irreducible Brillouin zone is utilized to simplify the modelling. The result is a differential eigenvalue problem, which is solved numerically using the commercial finite element program COMSOL Multiphysics.

A topology optimization problem is formulated with the objective of maximizing the photonic band gap. The optimization problem uses an active set strategy to obtain a smooth problem. The sensitivity analysis is performed for both single and multiple eigenvalues, and the resulting sensitivities are updated according to the symmetries of the crystal lattice being investigated. The optimization problem is implemented using a combination of Matlab and COMSOL, and the resulting program is verified by comparison to 1D analytical results. To improve performance, selected parts of the optimization problem is parallelized and a speedup of 5.75 for 7 CPUs is obtained.

The optimization program is then used to optimize photonic crystals, exemplified by the simple cubic and diamond lattices. It is demonstrated that the topology optimization method is an efficient tool for the design 3D photonic crystals, and that the optimized crystals display band gaps which are 2 to 20 percent larger than the best designs reported in the literature.

Resumé

Tre dimensionale fotoniske krystaller er en type af kunstigt fremstillede materialer med den egenskab at elektromagnetiske bølger, med vilkårlig polarisering, ikke udbredes for et bestemt frekvens interval. Dette speciale beskriver anvendelsen af topologi optimerings metoden til at designe 3D fotoniske krystaller med store bånd gab. Selvom ingen kendt teknologi kan fremstille 3D fotoniske krystaller i det synlige spektrum, er der mange potentielle anvendelses områder der kan føre til banebrydende fremskridt inden for f.eks. telekommunikation eller super computere i form af lys baserede transistorer. Formålet med dette speciale er således at formulere og implementere et optimerings problem, der kan anvendes til at designe 3D uendeligt periodiske fotoniske krystaller, og hvis muligt, at undersøge simplificerede designs baseret på resultater fra optimerings problemet.

De styrende ligninger for fotoniske krystaller bliver præsenteret i form af Maxwell ligningerne. Med antagelse af tidsharmonisk tids afhængighed og inklusion af Bloch bølge repræsentation bliver disse ligninger omskrevet, således at et differentielt egenværdi problem fremkommer. Tillige bliver den irreducerbare Brillouine zone introduceret for at simplificere modelleringen. Egenværdi problemet løses ved brug af det kommercielle finite element program COMSOL Multiphysics.

Dernæst formuleres et topologi optimerings problem, hvor kost funktionen har til formål at maksimere bånd gabets størrelse. For at opnå et glat optimerings problem anvendes en aktiv mængde strategi. Sensitivitets analysen bliver udledt, både for enkelte og multiple egenværdier, og de resulterende sensitiviteter bliver opdateret i henhold til symmetrierne for den iagttagede krystal struktur. Optimerings problemet bliver implementeret i en kombination af Matlab og COMSOL, og bliver verificeret ved sammenligning med analytiske resultater for et kendt 1D optimerings problem. Enkelte dele af programmet bliver paralleliseret for at opnå hurtigere løsnings tid. Dette giver en hastigheds forbedring på 5.75 ved brug af syv processorer.

Optimerings programmet bliver herefter anvendt til at optimere fotoniske krystaller, eksemplificeret ved simpel kubiske og diamant krystal strukturer. Det bliver eftervist at topologi optimerings metoden er et effektivt værktøj til design af 3D fotoniske krystaller. Endvidere har de optimerede designs bånd gab der er 2 til 20 procent større end de bedste design hidtil præsenteret i litteraturen.

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Introduction

The method of topology optimization was first proposed as a method for structural optimization in the late 1980's by [Bendsøe and Kikuchi, 1988], and has since then flourished to become a valuable engineering tool in many different areas of industrial application [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. The method is, however, no longer confined to structural optimization, and has been proven to be applicable in fields as diverse as fluid mechanics, MicroElectroMechanical Systems (MEMS) and acoustics [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. The success of the method makes it natural to try and expand its application to new branches of physics.

Since the turn of the millennium, the method has been applied to the design of structures and materials subject to wave propagation. The goal is to design periodic structures which prohibits the propagation of waves for a certain frequency range [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. A structure or material with this property is said to possess a band gap. This phenomenon is seen in both elastic and acoustic wave propagation where the material is said to have a phononic band gap, while in electromagnetics such a material is called a *photonic band gap crystal* [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. Though the method has already been shown to work for 2D problems [Sigmund and Jensen, 2003, Cox and Dobson, 2000], the extension to 3D topology optimization has not yet been pursued.

1.1 The Photonic Crystal

A photonic crystal is comprised of a periodic arrangement of macroscopic dielectric media, which affects the propagation of electromagnetic waves. Photonic band gap materials are a class of photonic crystals in which only certain frequencies can propagate. The basic characteristic of a photonic band gap crystal is, that it consists of (at least) two dielectric media with a dielectric contrast, e.g. silicon and air [Joannopoulos et al., 1995], and that the length-scale of the periodic cell is comparable to the wavelength, λ , of the electromagnetic wave, i.e. $\lambda \approx a$ where a is the lattice constant. This means that a photonic crystal in the visible spectrum should have nanometer dimensions. However, due to linearity of the physical law governing electromagnetic wave propagation, i.e. Maxwell's equations, a photonic crystal

(a) Unit cell of the simple cubic rectangular scaffold photonic crystal with a 7% band gap. Blue is silicon with $\epsilon = 13$ in an air background of $\epsilon = 1$.

(b) Unit cell of a diamond type photonic crystal with a 29% band gap. Blue is silicon with $\epsilon = 13$ in an air background of $\epsilon = 1$, where grey represents the cell boundaries.

Figure 1.1: Two illustrative examples of 3D photonic band gap crystals, c.f. Chapter 5 and 6 for details on the respective designs.

designed for the visible regime can be scaled and manufactured in millimeters for microwave applications [Busch et al., 2007].

The existence of a 1D band gap material was first studied and published by Lord Rayleigh in 1888 [Wikipedia, 2007], and the outcome was the well known multilayer film, or Bragg grating, which has a one dimensional band gap. It took almost 100 years before the possibility of 2D and 3D photonic crystals was suggested [Yablonovitch, 1987]. Yablonovitch was also the first to fabricate a 3D photonic crystal in the microwave regime, and verify that it had a 3D band gap¹ [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. As for the one dimensional case, the 2D and 3D photonic crystal are capable of 2D and 3D band gaps respectively. The 3D photonic crystal is naturally the most interesting of the three, since it can operate in the general setting of any angle of incidence and polarization of the waves, but it is likewise the most difficult to manufacture [Busch et al., 2007]. To illustrate the layout of 3D photonic band gap crystals two examples are shown in Figure 2.1. The scaffold crystal, Figure 1.1a, has a 7% complete band gap while the diamond like structure, Figure 1.1b, has a 29% complete band gap. The largest theoretical band gap known today for a silicon and air 3D photonic crystal is also a diamond like structure with a band gap of 31.4% which was reported in [Chern et al., 2007].

The 3D photonic band gap crystal has received growing interest during the last two decades. This is because it is expected that the phenomenon can be utilized in lens design as a perfect dielectric mirror, in communication devices as

¹This photonic crystal is today known as Yablonovite.

perfect waveguides or as light based transistors in photonic integrated circuits. [Busch et al., 2007]. Though the possible applications are both promising and plentiful, it must be emphasized that they are still far from realization. This is due to the present limitations in nano-fabrication techniques [Busch et al., 2007].

1.2 Classic Topology Optimization

The method of topology optimization is a numerical method to determine the optimal layout of a structure with respect to some qualitative measure. The method had its origin in structural optimization, and attacked the classical problem of distributing a limited amount of material in a design domain, such that the resulting structure is as stiff as possible [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. This problem is commonly known as the minimum compliance problem, with compliance being the inverse of stiffness.

However, the full potential of the method did not become apparent until the introduction of a non-linear material interpolation scheme, known as Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP) [Bendsøe, 1989], which ensures that the optimized designs are black and white. Here black and white refer to a design consisting of either material or void, contrary to a grey scale design in which several intermediate materials would have to be synthesised before fabrication. Though the SIMP method results in designs without intermediate materials, there was still problems with mesh dependency and checkerboards. This final frontier was overcome by the introduction of a sensitivity filter, e.g. [Sigmund, 1994], which made the method of topology optimization usefull for industrial applications.

1.3 Optimization of Photonic Crystals

In the past decade several papers have been published on the design and optimization of 2D photonic crystals, e.g. using standard gradient based topology optimization methods [Cox and Dobson, 1999], [Cox and Dobson, 2000] and [Sigmund and Jensen, 2003], by use of level set methods [Kao et al., 2005] and evolutionary algorithms [Preble et al., 2005]. The results from these studies showed that the method of topology optimization is capable of yielding good results in the design of 2D photonic crystals. The studies also showed that the optimization problem is prone to be non-smooth, and therefore that gradient based optimization methods should be used with caution [Kao et al., 2005].

Regarding topology optimization of 3D photonic crystals the picture is quite different, and to the authors knowledge no papers on the matter has been published. However, since the phenomenon of photonic band gap crystals has similarities to semi-conductors in solid-state physics [Kittel, 1996], several parameter studies based on atomic structures have been published, e.g. [Chern et al., 2007] and [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. In fact, it has been said that the theory of photonic crystals is a mixture of electromagnetism and solid-state physics [Busch et al., 2007].

Figure 1.2: Illustration of three important crystal lattices with respect to the design of 3D photonic crystals.

Therefore three of the most important atomic crystal lattices, with respect to the design of 3D photonic crystals, are illustrated in Figure 1.2. These, and possibly other, crystal structures constitute the backbone of 3D photonic crystal optimization, and they will be addressed in more detail later in this thesis.

1.4 Thesis objectives and Overview

Since no papers have been published on topology optimization of 3D photonic crystal, the main objective of this thesis is to investigate the application of topology optimization to the design of 3D photonic band gap crystal. When possible, the approach will be based on findings made for the 2D case.

Since fabrication of 3D photonic crystals is an active research area in itself, no effort will be made to assure that the optimized designs can be manufactured. Though if possible, simplifications of the designs will be made to capture the most important features of a given 3D photonic crystal.

Performing 3D numerical analysis is known to be extremely time consuming, and therefore effort will be made to parallelize selected parts of the developed optimization program.

The remainder of the report is organized as follows. First the basic theory of photonic crystals is presented, in which Maxwell's equations and their finite element solution are given, along with Bloch wave representation and the optimization problem to be solved. The next chapter deals with issues concerning the COMSOL [COMSOL, 2007] implementation, parallelization and verification of the numerical scheme. This is followed by a presentation and discussion of the opti-

mized designs for the simple cubic and diamond lattices. Finally the findings are summarized in a conclusion. The report is concluded with an Appendix containing mathematical derivations, extra material and selected parts of source code.

Topology Optimization of Photonic Crystals

The basic topology optimization approach consist of determining the optimal distribution of material, $\gamma(\mathbf{x})$, in a domain, Ω , such that an objective function $f(\gamma)$ is minimized (or maximized) [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. The objective function should be a scalar measure of the systems performance, e.g. the size of the photonic band gap, and must depend on the material distribution γ . Furthermore the optimized design γ_{opt} needs to obey the physical law governing the relevant problem, thus rendering the optimization problem a constrained problem. The governing equations are typically cast in the form of Partial Differential Equations (PDEs), for which closed form solutions does not exist in the general setting of complex geometries and material non-homogeneity. This is also the case when modelling photonic crystals, where Maxwell's equations constitutes the physical law. This motivates the application of an approximate solution method. In this thesis the Finite Element Method (FEM) is applied to discretize the domain Ω into N conforming elements [Zaglmayr, 2006]. Each element is given material parameters according to the function γ , thus leading to a discrete representation of the material distribution, i.e. $\gamma(x_e)$ for $e = 1, \dots, N$. As will become clear later, this spatial discretization of the domain is central to the method of topology optimization.

The final formulation of the topology optimization problem is posed using notation from mathematical programming. In the general setting such a formulation can be stated as

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{(NLP)} & \min_{\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^N} f(\gamma) \\ & \text{subject to } \gamma \in S \end{array}$$

where the feasible set S contains all possible γ that fullfills the constraints, e.g. the governing equations and bounds on the material choice. The solution of the optimization problem is usually found through application of gradient based optimization algorithms [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004, Andréasson et al., 2005].

Though this framework is very general and readily applies to several different branches of physics, fundamental knowledge of the underlying physical problem is paramount for a successful implementation. That is, numerical analysis returns very precise answers to very specific questions. Thus formulating the optimization

problem and interpreting the results, rely heavily on a sound understanding of the physical problem.

Therefore the remainder of this chapter is devoted to explaining the basic physics of photonic crystals as well as the governing equations and their FEM solution. Finally the optimization problem is posed on a form similar to the one given in (NLP) and its solution will be discussed.

2.1 Maxwell's Equations on Timeharmonic form

The physical law governing propagation of electromagnetic waves in a continuous medium in a domain, Ω , are described by Maxwell's five equations [Balanis, 1989]. Since the aim of this project is to model light propagation, it can be assumed that the time dependency is harmonic, i.e. the electric field $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \Re [\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})e^{j\omega t}]$, where ω is the frequency, $\mathbf{x}$ is a vector of space coordinates, t is the time, $j = \sqrt{-1}$ is the imaginary unit and $\Re$ denotes the real part.

Maxwell's equations on timeharmonic form for a linear and isotropic material can be written as a system of linear PDEs in only the electric field, $\mathbf{E}$, see Appendix A.2 for derivation.

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) + (j\omega\sigma - \omega^2\epsilon)\mathbf{E} &= -j\omega\mathbf{J}^{imp} \\ \nabla \cdot \epsilon\mathbf{E} &= \rho_e \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.1)$$

where σ is the conductivity, $\mathbf{J}^{imp}$ is a prescribed impressed current density and ρ_e is the electric charge density. The relative permittivity and relative permeability are real valued functions of the space coordinates, i.e. $\epsilon = \epsilon(\mathbf{x})$ and $\mu = \mu(\mathbf{x})$, while it is assumed that neither the dielectric function nor the permeability depends on time or frequency. The top equation is recognized as the vector Helmholtz equation, i.e. the vector wave equation [Jin, 2002]. A comparison to elastic wave propagation shows that the curl-curl term is similar to stiffness, $j\omega\sigma\mathbf{E}$ to damping and $\omega^2\epsilon\mathbf{E}$ to inertia. The bottom equation states that the net flux through the domain equals the electric charge density of the medium, which has the mechanical analogue of a compressible material in the mixed form of the elasticity equations, c.f. [Zienkiewicz and Taylor, 2000]. The system of PDEs in eqs. (2.1.1) together with appropriate boundary conditions forms a Boundary Value Problem (BVP) in the electric field. Having solved eqs. (2.1.1) for the electric field, the magnetic field is determined by the real part of

$$\mathbf{H} = \frac{-1}{j\omega\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \quad (2.1.2)$$

The formulation of Maxwell's equations in eqs. (2.1.1) is valid in both two and three dimensions, though the 2D case is usually simplified by differentiating between Transverse Electric (TE) modes and Transverse Magnetic (TM) modes

[Balanis, 1989]. This simplification leads to two independent problems both governed by the scalar Helmholtz equation [Demkowicz, 2003]. Thus modelling the 3D Maxwell problem is not a trivial expansion of the 2D case.

2.1.1 Modelling Photonic Crystals

Modelling wave propagation in a photonic crystal, is characterized by a domain filled with non-magnetic, $\mu \approx 1$, and non-conducting dielectric material, $\sigma = 0$, with piecewise constant ϵ and μ , without the presence of sources, i.e. $\mathbf{J}^{imp} = \mathbf{0}$ and $\rho_e = 0$ [Zaglmayr, 2006]. This leads to Maxwell's differential EigenValue Problem (EVP) which is given by

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) &= \omega^2 \epsilon \mathbf{E} \\ \nabla \cdot \epsilon \mathbf{E} &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (2.1.3)$$

Note that the divergence condition now states that there are no point sources in the medium. The EVP, together with appropriate boundary conditions, is to be solved for the eigenpairs $(\omega^2, \mathbf{E})$, where ω is the resonant frequency and $\mathbf{E}$ is the corresponding eigenmode. An effect of the linearity of the EVP is that Maxwell's equations do not have a fundamental lengthscale. For example by scaling the lengths by a factor s , i.e. $\tilde{\mathbf{x}} = s\mathbf{x}$, leads to a scaling of the frequencies of the same factor, i.e. $\tilde{\omega} = \omega/s$, while the eigenmodes are simply scaled by s [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. The scalability of Maxwell's equations is of major practical importance. That is, the solution of the EVP on one lengthscale determines solutions on all other lengthscales. Thus it is possible to design, manufacture and test a given photonic crystal in e.g. the microwave regime, for which the fabrication can be realized [Busch et al., 2007].

An important mathematical observation is that the EVP is Hermitian, i.e. multiplying by a vectorfield $\mathbf{F}$, integrating over the domain and performing integration by parts twice returns the original equation with $\mathbf{E}$ and $\mathbf{F}$ interchanged. This property can be used to identify the eigenvalues of the EVP as being real and that two distinct solutions $(\omega_1^2, \mathbf{E}_1)$ and $(\omega_2^2, \mathbf{E}_2)$ have orthogonal eigenmodes [Hansen, 2006]. It should be noted that multiple eigenvalues are very likely to occur when modelling photonic crystals. This is due to the high degree of symmetry that characterizes the dielectric function of a photonic crystal [Joannopoulos et al., 1995].

2.1.2 Bloch Boundary Conditions and the Band Structure

To complete the BVP and EVP stated above, one must impose boundary conditions (BCs). Since the objective of this project is to design periodic crystals the BCs are chosen to be periodic. The straightforward approach would be to impose Dirichlet conditions on all surfaces, such that the electric field on any surface is equal to the electric field on an opposite surface. This would however limit the solutions to being strictly periodic with the chosen base cell, Y , and as a consequence not provide a full description of the systems response to waves of arbitrary

wavelength, polarization and direction of propagation. To circumvent this limitation Bloch wave theory is introduced to the problem, i.e. the electric field modes are expressed as products of plane waves and a Y -periodic function, see Section 2.2 for details.

In electromagnetics the tangential component of the electric field must be continuous across a material interface [Balanis, 1989], while the normal components are allowed to be discontinuous. This leads to Dirichlet conditions involving the crossproduct and the full EVP including the Bloch wave representation can be formulated as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}_{nk}) - \omega_n^2(\mathbf{k}) \epsilon \mathbf{E}_{nk} &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega \\
 \nabla \cdot \epsilon \mathbf{E}_{nk} &= 0 && \text{in } \Omega \\
 \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{E}_{nk,i} &= \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{E}_{nk,p} e^{j\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}}|_{x=\mathbf{a}_p, \mathbf{k} \in K} && \text{on } \Gamma_{i,p} \\
 \forall \mathbf{k} \in K \text{ and } n = 1, 2, \dots, \infty &&&
 \end{aligned} \tag{2.1.4}$$

where the subscript $(\cdot)_{nk}$ refers to the n th mode associated with the wave vector $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ from the set K , i.e. for each wave vector a distinct EVP must be solved. The wave vector $\mathbf{k}$ and the construction of the set K will be explained in Section 2.2. For now it is adequate to simply assume, that the set K can be chosen such that the solution to the EVP(s) in eqs. (2.1.4) yields a complete description of the periodic system subjected to any wave with any wavelength and polarization. Considering the boundary conditions, the subscripts i and p refer to opposite surfaces and $\mathbf{n}$ is an outward unit normal. The lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}_p$ are dependent on both the geometry of the computational domain Ω , as well as the crystal lattice under investigation. This will be further discussed in Section 2.2. Also note that the formulation in eqs. (2.1.4) makes the electric field complex and that the physical solution is obtained by taking the real part of the result. Since the EVP is still Hermitian, the eigenvalues will still be purely real.

Having established that the modes in eqs. (2.1.4) can be classified by the wave vector $\mathbf{k}$, we are ready to define the band structure of the periodic crystal. First the modes for a given wave vector, $\mathbf{k}$, are ordered by increasing frequency, i.e. $\omega_1(\mathbf{k}) \leq \omega_2(\mathbf{k}) \leq \dots \leq \omega_n(\mathbf{k})$. Then by varying the wave vector continuously one would expect that each $\omega_n(\mathbf{k})$ also varies continuously as a function of $\mathbf{k}$. This is exactly what happens, see e.g. [Busch et al., 2007, Joannopoulos et al., 1995] for a proof, and the number n is defined as the band number. Thus by plotting the frequencies as functions of the wave vector the *band diagram* is generated. The band diagram is the backbone of interpreting and predicting the optical performance of a photonic crystal and two illustrative sketches of such diagrams are shown in Figure 2.1.

The band diagram of Figure 2.1 is to be interpreted in the following way. For a given frequency, $\tilde{\omega}$, the propagating modes are identified by the intersections of the horizontal line originating at $\tilde{\omega}$ and the band structure. Thus for a specific frequency there can be one, several or no propagating modes. For example Figure 2.1a shows that there are propagating modes for the whole frequency spectrum covered by the first eight bands, though band 3 and 4 never intersect. However if, for a given frequency or frequency range, there are no propagating modes regardless

(a) The first $n = 8$ bands for a fictitious material, without the presence of a band gap.

(b) The first $n = 13$ bands of a fictitious material, where a complete band gap is observed between bands 2 and 3 as illustrated by the grey rectangle.

Figure 2.1: The figures (a) and (b) are sketches of the typical layout of the band structure for a photonic crystal, for which the wave vector varies continuously within the set K .

of the wave vector $\mathbf{k}$, the gap that occurs is defined as the *photonic band gap*. This is illustrated by the grey rectangle in Figure 2.1b. It is the existence and size of these band gaps that are the main focus of this thesis. The size of the band gap is best measured using a relative gap indication, such that band gaps in different frequency spectra can be compared. It is standard in the photonic crystal literature to use the gap to midgap ratio [Joannopoulos et al., 1995, Maldovan and Thomas, 2004], i.e. the difference between the maximum value of band j and the minimum value of band $j + 1$, divided by the mean of the two as given in (2.1.5)

$$\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0} = 2 \frac{\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k - \max_k \omega_j^k}{\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k + \max_k \omega_j^k} \quad (2.1.5)$$

From Figure 2.1 it is also evident that many of the modes are degenerate, i.e. multiple eigenvalues, which can cause problems for both the solution of the EVP as well as for the optimization problem, see Sections 2.4.4, 3.1 and Appendix C.3 for more on this issue. Before presenting a method for the solution of Maxwell's EVP, eqs. (2.1.4), the Bloch wave representation, the wave vector $\mathbf{k}$, the set K and the lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}_p$ are to be explained in the upcoming section.

2.1.3 Origin of the Photonic Band Gap

This Section is intended to provide an intuitive way of understanding the origin of the photonic band gap.

For clarity the most important characteristics of a photonic crystal is repeated. A photonic crystal consists of a non-conducting, non-magnetic material, $\mu \approx 1 = \text{const.}$, with a piecewise constant dielectric function $\epsilon = \epsilon(x) = \{\epsilon_{high}, \epsilon_{low}\}$ where ϵ_{high} and ϵ_{low} are two different dielectric materials with a contrast, i.e. $\epsilon_{high} \neq \epsilon_{low}$. Since this Section is intended to provide a basic understanding of the band gap's origin, the problem is reduced to one dimension and the analysis is restricted to the case of TM modes. This results in the well known 1D wave equation, which can be solved for the dispersion relation using the assumption of timeharmonic time dependence and by applying the Bloch wave representation in space, i.e. $u(x) = v(x)e^{j\omega t}e^{jkx}$.

$$\frac{1}{\mu} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial t^2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon(x)} \frac{\partial^2 u}{\partial x^2} \Rightarrow \frac{\omega^2}{\mu} v(x) = \frac{k^2}{\epsilon(x)} v(x) \Rightarrow \omega(k) = \frac{k}{\sqrt{\mu\epsilon(x)}} \quad (2.1.6)$$

The final expression, $\omega(k) = \frac{k}{\sqrt{\mu\epsilon(x)}}$, is the dispersion relation, i.e. how much the light spreads out over time as seen in e.g. a prism [Kittel, 1996].

Using the dispersion relation it is possible to explain (without a proof) the origin of the photonic band gap. Consider two modes chosen such that one mode lies just above the band gap and the other lies just below. It can be shown, [Joannopoulos et al., 1995] that the energy of the lower mode is concentrated in regions of high permittivity, i.e. ϵ_{high} , and thus yielding a low frequency by use of eq. 2.1.6. The opposite holds for the upper mode, i.e. its energy is usually concentrated in the ϵ_{low} regions or at interfaces between ϵ_{high} and ϵ_{low} . This means that the effective permittivity is low and thereby raising the frequency in eq. 2.1.6. This is the basic mechanism that causes the presence of a band gap.

Since most photonic crystals are build of a high dielectric material, e.g. silicon, in an air background, the upper and lower bands are sometimes referred to as the *air-band* and *dielectric-band* respectively.

A 3D illustration of this phenomenon can be seen in Appendix E, and an indepth discussion as well as mathematical reasoning can be found in [Joannopoulos et al., 1995].

2.2 Bloch Functions and the Brillouin Zone

When solving the EVP on a base cell Y using standard periodic BCs, one will always obtain Y -periodic modes. This is however not consistent with the real world, where many other modes of propagation are possible. Therefore the theory of Bloch waves are applied to the eigensolutions. The Bloch theorem [Kittel, 1996] states that for a infinite periodic medium, the eigenfunctions can be expressed as a plane wave times a cell periodic function, i.e.

$$\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x})e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} \quad (2.2.1)$$

where $\mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{v}(\mathbf{x} + Y)$ is Y -periodic and $\mathbf{k} \in \mathbb{R}^3$ is the wave vector. Here it should also be noted that only the real part of $\mathbf{u}(\mathbf{x})$ has physical meaning. An

Figure 2.2: 1D illustration of the Bloch wave representation of $v(x) = \sin(x\frac{2\pi}{a}) + \frac{1}{2}$ plotted for four different values of k . The black graph shows the real part of the Bloch wave function and the red graph is the real part of the plane wave $e^{jk \cdot x}$. The blue lines illustrates one unit cell.

example of such a function in photonic crystals is the electric field mode, i.e. $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{Y})$ ¹. Also note that by varying the wave vector, the eigenmodes can take on any kind of periodicity in all directions with wavelengths larger or equal to base cell Y .

The extended periodicity can be illustrated by a simple 1D example, e.g $v(x) = \sin(x\frac{2\pi}{a}) + \frac{1}{2}$ which has periodicity a . In Figure 2.2 the corresponding Bloch function as well as the plane wave modulation $e^{jk \cdot x}$ is shown for four different values of the wave vector. By inspection of the real part of $e^{jk \cdot x}$ in Figure 2.2, i.e. the red lines, one finds that this modulation contributes to an altering of the wavelength of the original Y -periodic function. That is, $k = \pi$ yields a $2Y$ -periodic function as seen in Figure 2.2d, while smaller wavenumbers results in Bloch functions with longer wavelength. From Figure 2.2 it can also be seen that the Bloch wave function is not just an elongation of the original Y -periodic function, but that the waveform is modulated according to eq. (2.2.1). This means for example that $k = 0$ and

¹Could also be the $\mathbf{H}$ -field

$k = 2\pi$ does not produce the same waveform, though both have a period of Y .

Now a question naturally arise: are there any restrictions on the choice of wave vectors, or do we have to compute solutions for all (infinitely many!) to obtain a complete description of the dispersion relation for a given photonic crystal? The answer is, fortunately, that there *are* restrictions on the wave vector, such that only a finite set has to be evaluated. In order to appreciate the reason for this, some basic crystal lattice properties must be introduced.

2.2.1 The Crystal Lattice

A primitive cell is a minimum-volume cell, which means that it is the smallest possible repetitive volume that makes up the crystal structure. The primitive cell is furthermore characterized by containing only one lattice point. The notion of lattice points is most easily understood by considering atomic crystals, where an atom is situated on each lattice point. Closely related to the primitive cell are the primitive lattice vectors, which span the primitive cell [Kittel, 1996]. For the case of the simple cubic (sc) lattice in a cube of sidelength a , these vectors are given by

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = a\mathbf{e}_x + 0\mathbf{e}_y + 0\mathbf{e}_z, \quad \mathbf{a}_2 = 0\mathbf{e}_x + a\mathbf{e}_y + 0\mathbf{e}_z, \quad \mathbf{a}_3 = 0\mathbf{e}_x + 0\mathbf{e}_y + a\mathbf{e}_z \quad (2.2.2)$$

where a is the lattice constant and $\mathbf{e}_x$, $\mathbf{e}_y$ and $\mathbf{e}_z$ are unit vectors in the Cartesian coordinate system. Note that in the case of a unit cube the lattice constant is unity, i.e. $a = 1$. For the face centered cubic (fcc) lattice the primitive lattice vectors are given by

$$\mathbf{a}_1 = \frac{1}{2}a(\mathbf{e}_x + \mathbf{e}_y), \quad \mathbf{a}_2 = \frac{1}{2}a(\mathbf{e}_y + \mathbf{e}_z), \quad \mathbf{a}_3 = \frac{1}{2}a(\mathbf{e}_x + \mathbf{e}_z) \quad (2.2.3)$$

The sc lattice vectors and primitive cell are illustrated in Figure 2.3a and the equivalent for the fcc system in Figure 2.4a.

2.2.2 The Reciprocal Lattice and the Brillouin Zone

Every crystal structure has, besides the crystal lattice, also a reciprocal lattice associated with it. The reciprocal lattice lies in Fourier space, i.e. the space of wave vectors which is the space-dimension analogue to time and frequency, and therefore has dimensions $[1/m]$. Thus the reciprocal lattice can be constructed using Fourier transformation of $\mathbf{x}$ -space into $\mathbf{k}$ -space. Applying Fourier analysis to a Y -periodic function, e.g. $\epsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \epsilon(\mathbf{x} + Y)$, yields that the condition $e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot Y} = 1$ must hold [Kittel, 1996], see Appendix D.2 for a short description. This is satisfied for $\mathbf{k}\cdot Y = 2n\pi$ where n is an integer [Busch et al., 2007, Kittel, 1996]. Denoting the wave vectors, $\mathbf{k}$, that fulfill this relation by $\mathbf{G}$, the reciprocal lattice is defined.

There is, however, a simple geometric relation between the crystal lattice and reciprocal lattice, which can be expressed using the following formula [Kittel, 1996]

$$\mathbf{b}_1 = 2\pi \frac{\mathbf{a}_2 \times \mathbf{a}_3}{\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 \times \mathbf{a}_3}, \quad \mathbf{b}_2 = 2\pi \frac{\mathbf{a}_3 \times \mathbf{a}_1}{\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 \times \mathbf{a}_3}, \quad \mathbf{b}_3 = 2\pi \frac{\mathbf{a}_1 \times \mathbf{a}_2}{\mathbf{a}_1 \cdot \mathbf{a}_2 \times \mathbf{a}_3} \quad (2.2.4)$$

(a) sc lattice and primitive cell with sidelength a . Lattice points are at vertexes. (b) First Brillouin zone for sc with sidelength $2\pi/a$. Lattice points are cell centered.

Figure 2.3: sc lattice and its reciprocal lattice. The black dots represent lattice points and the blue lines are the lattice vectors (a) and reciprocal lattice vectors (b)

(a) fcc lattice and primitive cell in a unit cube. Blue lines are the primitive lattice vectors, while the remaining primitive cell is illustrated by red lines, which forms a rhombohedral. (b) First Brillouin zone for fcc in a cube of sidelength $4\pi/a$. The blue lines that span the first Brillouin zone forms a truncated octahedron

Figure 2.4: fcc lattice and its reciprocal lattice. Black dots represents lattice points and the black lines forms the associated cubic cell.

Note that if the lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}_i$ spans a primitive cell in real space, then the reciprocal lattice vectors also spans a primitive cell, but this time in reciprocal space. Now by combining the periodicity of the wave vector, $\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{Y} = 2n\pi$, with the Bloch wave representation of the electric field

$$\mathbf{E}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x}) = \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x})e^{j\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} = \bar{\mathbf{E}}_{\mathbf{k}}(\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{Y})e^{j\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{x}} \quad (2.2.5)$$

it is clear that some wave vectors will yield the same modes, i.e. when $\mathbf{k} = \mathbf{k} + \mathbf{G}$. Thus it is only necessary to consider wave vectors within the primitive cell in reciprocal space to fully describe the dispersion relation of a infinitely periodic crystal. This leads to the definition of the first Brillouin zone, which is defined as a primitive cell in reciprocal space [Kittel, 1996]. As the name implies there are more Brillouin zones, which will not be discussed further in this thesis, since they are of no relevance to the subject of band gaps in photonic crystals.

Using eqs. (2.2.4) the first Brillouin zone for the sc lattice is seen to also be a simple cubic lattice with lattice constant $2\pi/a$. See Fig. 2.3b for illustration. The reciprocal to the fcc lattice is not as simple. Here the reciprocal lattice becomes the following upon insertion in eqs. (2.2.4)

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{b}_1 &= 2\pi/a(-\mathbf{e}_x + \mathbf{e}_y + \mathbf{e}_z), & \mathbf{b}_2 &= 2\pi/a(\mathbf{e}_x - \mathbf{e}_y + \mathbf{e}_z), \\ \mathbf{b}_3 &= 2\pi/a(\mathbf{e}_x + \mathbf{e}_y - \mathbf{e}_z) \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.6)$$

These translation vectors are recognized as the primitive lattice vectors of a body centered cubic (bcc) crystal in a cube with sidelength $4\pi/a$, i.e. the bcc is reciprocal to fcc lattice [Kittel, 1996]. The first Brillouin zone for the fcc crystal is illustrated in Figure 2.4b.

2.2.3 The Irreducible Brillouin Zone

The set of wave vectors within the first Brillouin zone can be reduced further using symmetry assumptions on the primitive cell. For the cubic lattices there are a total of nine symmetry planes, which reduces the Brillouin zone to 1/48 of its original size. This approach is widely used, c.f. [Busch et al., 2007] or [Joannopoulos et al., 1995], and the points of high symmetry has been given names [Kittel, 1996][Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. For the sc lattice the points are $\Gamma - X - M - R$, which together with the irreducible Brillouin zone are shown in Fig. 2.5. For the fcc lattice the points are commonly known as $\Gamma - X - U - W - K - L$ and the irreducible zone can be seen in Figures 2.6. The actual values of the wave vector at high symmetry points for the sc and fcc lattices are given in Appendix D.1. In theory all points within the irreducible Brillouin zone should be evaluated using eq. (2.2.1). However it is commonly used and accepted that only the lines connecting high symmetry points needs to be included, in order to obtain a complete description of the band structure [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004, Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. This reduced set of wave vectors is exactly the set K presented in eq. (2.1.4).

Figure 2.5: Irreducible Brillouin zone (black) and points of high symmetry for the sc lattice.

Figure 2.6: Irreducible Brillouin zone (red) and points of high symmetry for the fcc lattice.

2.2.4 Density of States

The symmetry considerations, as well as the heuristic assumption of lines connecting the high symmetry points in the Brillouin zone, provides a computational cheap way of determining $\omega_n(\mathbf{k})$ and thereby the size of the photonic band gap. However, if one wants to prove the existence and size of a photonic band gap, this requires the computation of the photonic density of states (DOS) [Busch et al., 2007].

The DOS is computed based on a uniform discretization of the wave vectors within the whole first Brillouin zone, and is given values by counting the number of allowed modes per unit increase in frequency. In the limit where the unit increase becomes infinitesimal, the DOS can be expressed as

$$\text{DOS}(\omega) = \sum_n \int_{\text{BZ}} \delta(\omega - \omega_n(\mathbf{k})) d\mathbf{k} \quad (2.2.7)$$

where $\delta(x)$ is the Dirac delta function and BZ denotes the Brillouin zone. A photonic band gap is then characterized by having a zero DOS, which can be seen illustrated in Figure 2.8b.

The DOS is a useful tool for verifying not only the high symmetry point assumption, but also that a given design fulfills the symmetries of the crystal lattice being investigated.

2.2.5 Inclusion of Bloch waves in Maxwell's equations

The inclusion of Bloch wave representation in Maxwell's EVP, can be done both through a modification of the differential operators, c.f. [Busch et al., 2007], or by modifying the boundary conditions. In this report the latter approach is used as shown in eqs. (2.1.4). And to complete this approach the lattice vectors $\mathbf{a}_p$ from eqs. (2.1.4) needs to be explained.

$\mathbf{a}_p$	sc	fcc
$\mathbf{a}_1$	$(a, 0, 0)$	$\frac{1}{2}(a, 0, a)$
$\mathbf{a}_2$	$(0, a, 0)$	$\frac{1}{2}(0, a, a)$
$\mathbf{a}_3$	$(0, 0, a)$	$\frac{1}{2}(a, a, a)$

Table 2.1: Lattice vectors used for the Bloch BCs on a cube of sidelength a in eqs. (2.1.4).

The lattice vectors need not be primitive, but are determined based on the computational domain and the crystal lattice at hand. In this thesis cubic cells of unity are used, which means that the lattice constant for both sc and fcc is $a = 1$. This means that the lattice vectors needed for the Bloch boundary conditions are exactly the primitive lattice vectors of the respective crystal lattices, see Table 2.1. The reader is referred to e.g. [Chern et al., 2007] for an example of an alternative choice of lattice vectors and computational domain.

Figure 2.7: Scaffold structure of dielectric material with $\epsilon = 13$ in air ($\epsilon = 1$), computed on a $16 \times 16 \times 16$ mesh. The structure has symmetry of the sc lattice.

2.2.6 The Photonic Band Gap Crystal

An example of a photonic band gap crystal with sc translational symmetry is shown in Figure 2.7. The corresponding band diagram is shown in Figure 2.8a, where the grey area shows the presence of a complete band gap of gap to midgap ratio $\Delta\omega/\omega_0 = 0.07$, in which no modes can propagate. In Figure 2.8b the DOS map shows that the assumption of only evaluating the EVP at wave vectors which lies on the lines connecting the high symmetry points of the irreducible Brillouin zone, provides a full description of the photonic crystals behaviour.

The presented example is based on a dielectric contrast of $\epsilon_2/\epsilon_1 = 13$, and a filling ratio of $\beta = 0.18$. The filling ratio β refers to the volume fraction of ϵ_2 -type material. The contrast, $\epsilon_2/\epsilon_1 = 13$, has been chosen since it corresponds to silicon and air, which are the preferred building blocks in fabrication of photonic crystals [Busch et al., 2007]. Moreover, this contrast makes it possible to compare results of this thesis to results from the literature. The contrast between the two dielectrics is of utmost importance, partly since a design consisting of purely ϵ_1 or ϵ_2 material has never been shown to possess a band gap [Busch et al., 2007, Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. And furthermore since structures with a high dielectric contrast tends to have larger band gaps than lower contrast materials [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. The permeabilities of such dielectric materials are approximately unity, i.e. the materials are non-magnetic [Balanis, 1989].

2.2.7 Symmetry Requirements on the Design

It is important to note that the reduction of the Brillouin zone is based on symmetry considerations regarding the photonic crystal, i.e. the crystal lattice, and therefore that it is imperative that the photonic crystal analyzed fulfills these symmetry requirements. If the symmetry requirements are not fulfilled, the band diagram based on the irreducible Brillouin zone can lead to serious misinterpreta-

(a) Band structure where the grey zone illustrates a 7% band gap and the x-axis shows the path through high symmetry points of the Brillouin zone.

(b) Density of states where 4960 equally spaced points within the irreducible Brillouin have been evaluated.

Figure 2.8: Band diagram (a) and density of states (b) based on rectangular scaffold structure with symmetries of the sc lattice, c.f. Figure 2.7. The dielectric contrast is based on silicon and air, i.e. $\epsilon_2/\epsilon_1 = 13$. Note that multiple frequencies are more frequent in high symmetry points then elsewhere.

tions of the photonic crystals optical properties. If one has doubts as to whether or not the symmetries are fulfilled, the problem can in most cases be remedied by computing a DOS map, though this, as will be become clear in Chapter 3, is an extremely costly process with respect to CPU time.

The symmetry requirements for the different type of lattice systems investigated in this thesis, will be presented together with the optimized designs, c.f. Chapter 5 and 6.

2.3 Finite Element Formulation of Maxwell's EVP

The differential EVP stated in (2.1.4) only posses closed form solutions for a few simple cases, and not for the general case of non-homogeneous ϵ and μ . This motivates the application of an approximate solution method, e.g. the finite difference method, method of moments etc. The choice in this thesis is to use the Finite Elements Method (FEM), in which, the original strong form of the PDE is put on a so-called weak or variational form, for which solutions exists and can be approximated numerically. The weak form is derived using the standard Galerkin method, and includes the divergence condition to stabilize the numerical scheme, see Appendix B for full derivation. Suppressing the subscript $(\cdot)_{nk}$ for simplicity, the variational problem becomes to find $\omega^2 \in R^+$, $\mathbf{E} \in H(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ and $\psi \in H^1(\Omega)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{F})^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \cdot \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \nabla \psi \, d\Omega = 0 \\ \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \nabla \phi^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \quad (2.3.1) \\ \forall \mathbf{F} \in H_0(\text{curl}, \Omega) \quad \text{and} \quad \forall \phi \in H_0^1(\Omega) \end{aligned}$$

where the superscript $(\cdot)^H$ denotes the complex conjugate transpose and $\mathbf{F}$ are test functions for the electric field, while ϕ are test functions for the Lagrange multipliers used to enforce the divergence condition. This type of problem is recognized as a mixed FE formulation or a saddle point problem [Jin, 2002]. The Sobolev space $H(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ consists of functions where both the functions themselves and their curl are square integrable in the Lebesgue sense, i.e. have a finite energy. Similarly $\psi \in H^1(\Omega)$ means that both ψ and $\nabla \psi$ are square integrable. Based on eq. (2.3.1) this requirement makes sense, since it prevents the integrals, or energies, from becoming infinite. Finally the subscript $(\cdot)_0$ for the test functions, means that these functions are zero on surfaces with Dirichlet conditions [Zaglmayr, 2006]. This is similar to the requirement in the principle of virtual work, where the virtual displacement field must be kinematically admissible [Cook et al., 2002].

In order to implement this numerically the continuous Sobolev spaces, $H(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ and $H^1(\Omega)$, are replaced by their discrete counterparts, and the domain of interest is discretized into N conforming finite elements. In order to accurately model the interface conditions or BCs as well as the curl operator, edge elements are used for the electric field expansion, see more on edge elements in Section 3.1.4. The scalar field is expanded using standard nodal basis functions as known from e.g. solid mechanics. The expansions are given in eq. (2.3.2)

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}) \approx \sum_{e=1}^N \mathbf{N}_E^e(\mathbf{x}) \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e \quad \text{and} \quad \psi(\mathbf{x}) \approx \sum_{e=1}^N \mathbf{N}_{\psi}^e(\mathbf{x}) \tilde{\psi}^e \quad (2.3.2)$$

where $\mathbf{N}_E$ and $\mathbf{N}_{\psi}$ are the shape function matrices for the electric field and Lagrange multipliers respectively and N is the number of elements in the mesh. The

vectors $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$ and $\tilde{\boldsymbol{\psi}}$ contains the expansion coefficients to be determined. The standard Galerkin method is completed by using the same expansion functions for the test fields as for the solution fields. Upon insertion and reentering of the wave vector dependence this leads to the algebraic EVP

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}^H & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{nk} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\psi}}_{nk} \end{Bmatrix} = \omega_n^2(\mathbf{k}) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \tilde{\mathbf{E}}_{nk} \\ \tilde{\boldsymbol{\psi}}_{nk} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (2.3.3)$$

which should be accompanied by an extra equation containing a normalization scheme for the eigenvectors, since these are only determined up to a multiplicative factor. The algebraic EVP in (2.3.3) is recognized as a generalized eigenvalue problem. Furthermore it is positive semi-definite [Zaglmayr, 2006], which means e.g. that a Cholesky factorization cannot be used in the solution process. General for the standard FE formulation is that the Dirichlet conditions are not included in the discretized equations [Cook et al., 2002] and must therefore be handled using separate techniques, see Section 3.1.4. And in order to obtain a consistent formulation, the Bloch boundary conditions must also be applied to the auxiliary field $\boldsymbol{\psi}$. One should also note that $\boldsymbol{\psi}$ only enters the problem through its gradient, c.f. eq. (2.3.1), and therefore a scaling condition is enforced through an artificial Dirichlet condition, e.g. $\boldsymbol{\psi} = 1$ in $\partial\Omega^*$ where $\partial\Omega^*$ is a single point in the domain Ω .

To finalize the discretization procedure the continuous set of wave vectors, following the path through the high symmetry points of the irreducible Brillouin zone, also needs to be discretized into a finite set.

2.4 The Optimization Problem

Now having established a basic understanding of photonic band gap crystals, as well as a method by which their properties can be modelled, the optimization problem is to be formulated. This will be done following the scheme outlined in the beginning of this chapter.

The goal in topology optimization of photonic band gap crystals is to determine the material distribution with the largest possible gap between band j and $j + 1$. This means that the gap to midgap ratio, eq. (2.1.5), is an obvious candidate for an objective function. For clarity the expression is restated below

$$f = \frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0} = 2 \frac{\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k - \max_k \omega_j^k}{\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k + \max_k \omega_j^k} \quad (2.4.1)$$

The next step is to introduce a material dependence to the problem. Recalling that a photonic band gap crystal always consists of (at least) two dielectric materials with different permittivities, i.e. $\epsilon_1 \neq \epsilon_2$, the design problem becomes to distribute $\epsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \{\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2\}$ for all $\mathbf{x} \in \Omega$, such that f is maximized. This direct approach poses two severe problems. The first problem is that the dielectric function needs

to be determined for every point in the design domain Ω , which results in an optimization problem with an infinite number of variables. The second problem is that the dielectric function is discrete valued, i.e. can take on either ϵ_1 or ϵ_2 , which leads to an integer optimization problem for which state of the art solution methods are limited to extremely small problems [Andréasson et al., 2005].

The first issue is cured by the spatial discretization. This reduces the number of points in Ω to a finite number, e.g. one per element. Thus the continuous dielectric function is replaced by a piecewise constant function $\epsilon_e = \{\epsilon_1, \epsilon_2\}$ for $e = 1, \dots, N$ where N is the number of elements in the FE-mesh.

The dielectric function is however still discrete valued. A remedy for this problem is to relax the material formulation. This is a standard part of the topology optimization method, and is done by introducing an extra field variable to the problem, a so-called design variable, which is free to vary continuously between zero and one, i.e. $\gamma_e \in [0; 1]$ for $e = 1, \dots, N$. The discrete dielectric function is then replaced by a continuous function where the design variables are used to interpolate linearly between ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , thus yielding

$$\epsilon_e = (1 - \gamma_e)\epsilon_1 + \gamma_e\epsilon_2, \quad e = 1, N \quad (2.4.2)$$

The interpolation results in an effective ϵ , that can take on values in between ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 , which again means that intermediate materials might be present in optimized designs. This issue is also addressed in the literature [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004, Sigmund and Jensen, 2003], where it is found that generally designs tend to be 0-1 upon convergence. This can be explained by the fact that the band gap tends to be bigger, the higher the contrast between ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 gets, thus rendering intermediate values inefficient for the optimizer. This is contrary to the classical minimum compliance problem, see a short description of this optimization problem in Appendix C.4, where the non-linear SIMP interpolation scheme was needed to obtain black and white designs.

As stated earlier the permeabilities for common dielectrics are approximately one, which means that they can be regarded as constant, i.e. $\mu_e = 1$ for $e = 1, \dots, N$. Thus there is no need to interpolate the permeability as done for dielectric function.

The optimization problem can now be stated on standard form as

$$(P) \quad \begin{array}{ll} \max_{\mathbf{E}_{nk}, \omega_n(\mathbf{k}), \gamma \in \mathbb{R}^N} & f(\gamma) = \frac{\Delta\omega(\gamma)}{\omega_0(\gamma)} \\ \text{subject to} & \left(\tilde{\mathbf{K}} - \omega_n^2(\mathbf{k})\tilde{\mathbf{M}}(\gamma) \right) \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{nk} = \mathbf{0}, \quad k \in K \\ & 0 \leq \gamma_e \leq 1, \quad \text{for } e = 1, N \end{array}$$

where N is the number of design variables, n is the number of computed bands and K is the set containing the symmetry lines of the reduced Brillouin zone, see Fig. 2.5. The EVP $\left(\tilde{\mathbf{K}} - \omega_n^2(\mathbf{k})\tilde{\mathbf{M}}(\gamma) \right) \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{nk} = \mathbf{0}$ is short hand notation for Maxwell's algebraic EVP in eq. (2.3.3), where it is also shown that the design or material dependence is introduced through the mass matrix. The problem (P) is observed to not be in need of a volume constraint, since a pure ϵ_1 or ϵ_2 design cannot

display a band gap. The lack of the volume constraint is another reason for why the SIMP material interpolation is useless, c.f. Appendix C.4. It is worth noting that the optimization problem (P) is almost identical to the two dimensional case [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004], i.e. the only difference is the governing equations.

Now having formulated the optimization problem, it is time to consider its solvability. First the optimization problem (P) is seen to be non-linear in the design variables. Moreover the problem is a double min-max optimization problem, i.e. the objective is non-smooth and hence non-differentiable. Since (P) is to be solved using a gradient based optimization algorithm, this poses a severe problem. So in order to use gradient based optimization algorithms, modifications to (P) have to be made.

2.4.1 Reformulation using Active Set Strategy

In order to obtain a smooth optimization problem, the straight forward approach would be to recast (P) on a bound formulation. In the bound formulation the objective function is replaced by a smooth function, and the original min-max function is split up into two times $k \in K$ constraints, see (P)₀ in Appendix C.1 for details. Though the bound formulation leads to a well posed optimization problem with respect to differentiability, this approach is not pursued further in this thesis. This is due to prior results and experiences found in the photonic (and phonon) optimization literature e.g. [Sigmund and Jensen, 2003, Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004].

From empirical knowledge regarding the 2D design of photonic crystals, it has been observed that the indices which minimizes and maximizes the terms in non-smooth objective function are almost constant throughout the optimization process. That is

$$\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k = \omega_{j+1}^{k_{\min}} \quad \text{and} \quad \max_k \omega_j^k = \omega_j^{k_{\max}}$$

where $k_{\min}$ and $k_{\max}$ are constant most of the time. This observation is also true for the findings of this thesis, and will be commented upon when presenting the optimized designs in the following chapters. The heuristic approach is then simply to assume that the objective function can be regarded as a smooth function, and use it unchanged in the optimization problem.

To further ensure that the indices $k_{\min}$ and $k_{\max}$ changes as little as possible during the optimization process, extra constraints are added to the problem formulation of the form

$$\omega_{\geq j}^k - \max_k \omega_j^k \leq 0 \quad \text{and} \quad \min_k \omega_{j+1}^k - \omega_{\leq j+1}^k \leq 0 \quad (2.4.5)$$

where the subscripts $(\cdot)_{\geq j}$ and $(\cdot)_{\leq j+1}$ refers to frequency bands below and above the gap j respectively. This is illustrated in Figure 2.9 where the blue crosses refer to $\frac{\min_k}{k} \omega_{j+1}^k$ and $\frac{\max_k}{k} \omega_j^k$ and the red spheres shows the new constraints given in eq. (2.4.5). Thus if $\frac{\max_k}{k} \omega_j^k$ becomes smaller, the constraints $(\cdot)_{\geq j}$ makes sure that the remaining lower bands does not exceed this value.

Figure 2.9: Illustration of the active set strategy, where the blue crosses refer to $\frac{\min}{k}\omega_{j+1}^k$ and $\frac{\max}{k}\omega_j^k$. The red spheres are the active constraints, i.e. below the band gap the red spheres refer to $\omega_{\geq j} \in \hat{K}$ and above the gap to $\omega_{\leq j+1} \in \hat{K}$.

From Figure 2.9 it can also be seen that not all $\omega_{\geq j}^k$ and $\omega_{\leq j+1}^k$ are included as constraints. In fact, only the M frequencies closest to $\frac{\min}{k}\omega_{j+1}^k$ and $\frac{\max}{k}\omega_j^k$ are taken into account. This is known as an active set strategy. The active set concept is widely used in mathematical programming, e.g. quadratic programming, and is basically a method used to reduced the number of inequality constraints in an optimization problem at iterate m [Andréasson et al., 2005]. That is, instead of considering all constraints at iterate m , only the constraints which restricts the choice of descent direction are included. Thus the active set can change from iterate to iterate, and to distinguish the active set from the full set of wave vectors, it is denoted by $\hat{K}$.

Finally a standard trick in topology optimization is applied to (P). Here the algebraic EVP is removed from optimization formulation, i.e. $(\mathbf{E}_{nk}, \omega_n(\mathbf{k}))$ are no longer included in the list of optimization variables. This can be done as given in [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004], by letting the computation of the objective and the solution of the state problem be part of the same function call, i.e. for a given iterate γ^m , the eigenpairs $(\mathbf{E}_{nk}^m, \omega_n^m(\mathbf{k}))$ are uniquely defined. The final optimization problem then becomes as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \max_{\gamma \in \mathbb{R}^N} && f(\gamma) = \frac{\Delta\omega(\gamma)}{\omega_0(\gamma)} \\
 \text{(P)}_1 & \text{ s.t.} && \min_k \omega_{j+1}^k - \omega_{\leq j+1}^h \leq 0 \quad h = 1, \dots, M \\
 & && \omega_{\geq j}^h - \max_k \omega_j^k \leq 0 \quad h = 1, \dots, M \\
 & && 0 \leq \gamma_e \leq 1, \quad \text{for } e = 1, N
 \end{aligned}$$

Note that the problem $(P)_1$ is subjected to $2M$ inequality constraints from the active set $\hat{K}$.

2.4.2 Solving the Optimization Problem

When attempting to solve the optimization problem $(P)_1$ with gradient based optimization algorithms, some properties are of special importance. It is seen that $(P)_1$ is a constrained, non-linear and non-convex optimization problem [Stolpe, 2007] [Andréasson et al., 2005]. The non-linear property implies that a general non-linear optimization algorithm must be used, while the non-convexity implies that the identification of a global minimum is not possible [Andréasson et al., 2005].

A common feature for non-linear optimization algorithms is that they solve $(P)_1$ iteratively until a Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) point is reached. A KKT-point can be thought of as a stationary point with respect to the objective as well as the constraints. Here the definition of convexity plays a role, since for convex problems, local and global minimums coincide. For a non-convex and non-linear optimization problem, the KKT conditions only tells that a local minimum is found, i.e. there may be other and better designs [Andréasson et al., 2005]. Therefore the optimization process should be started with several different initial guesses, such that the risk of converging to a local minimum is minimized.

The solver used in this project is the Method of Moving Asymptotes (MMA) developed by K. Svanberg [Svanberg, 1998], which can be obtained free of charge for academic usage. Furthermore MMA has been shown to be an effective method for the type of problem given in $(P)_1$ [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. In few words this algorithm uses gradient information at iteration m to set up an approximate subproblem consisting of strictly convex and separable functions. This subproblem is then solved using an interior point method until a KKT point is reached. It can be proven for the MMA subproblem that an optimal solution always exists, see [Svanberg, 1987] for details. The new design returned by the MMA algorithm is used to compute new objective, constraints and gradients. The process is then repeated until a convergence criterion is met, see Section 3.2 for the implemented stopping criteria.

2.4.3 Determining the Active Set

The application of the active set strategy requires that the number M of frequencies close to the objective frequencies is determined either a priori or dynamically at each optimization iteration. In this thesis M is chosen a priori, though in either case the choice depends both on the discretization of the wave vector in the irreducible Brillouin zone, as well as the layout of the band diagram. Generally speaking M should be chosen to be as little as possible, since this, to the authors experience, yields faster convergence.

There is however another issue that needs to be addressed when determining the active set. For a given initial design there are two general layouts of the band structure with respect to the gap of interest. Either the two bands of interest are separated throughout the irreducible Brillouin zone, or the two bands intersect. These situations are illustrated in Figures 2.10b and 2.10a respectively.

Figure 2.10: Illustration of how the active set is chosen, either based on the zipper approach (a), or the full spectrum of wave vectors (b), when the gap of interest lies between the second and third frequency bands.

If the two bands of interest do not intersect or a gap is already present, the task is merely to choose a suitable value of M . At each iteration in the optimization process, the $2M$ frequencies closest to the objective frequencies of the upper and lower band is determined and included as constraints, c.f. $(P)_1$ as well as Figure 2.10b and 2.9.

If no gap is present or the bands of interest intersect, the so-called zipper-approach is used to open a gap. Here the active set is confined to the part of Brillouin zone in which no intersection occurs, see Figure 2.10a. Based on this restricted spectrum, the objective and constraints are set up analogues to the method described above. Hopefully this leads to a separation of the bands of interest, and if that is the case, the process is stopped and a new active set is defined and the optimization is continued.

This all points to the fact that the optimization process is interactive, in the sense that choices made by the user are imperative to success of the scheme, and ultimately which local minimum is reached. Therefore, when applying the zipper method, one should try to open the desired gap by choosing different zipper regions.

2.4.4 Sensitivity Analysis

In order to use the gradient based optimization algorithm MMA for solving $(P)_1$, the gradients of the objective function and constraint functions with respect to the design variables must be computed. In constrained optimization these gradients are usually known as *sensitivities*, and the determination of them is termed sensitivity analysis [Andréasson et al., 2005].

The sensitivities of the objective and the constraint functions in (P)₁ with respect to the design variables, consist of finding the same key sensitivity, that is $d\omega_j^k/d\gamma$. Assuming $(\omega_j^k, \mathbf{E}_j)$ is a unique eigenpair and using that the mass matrix $\mathbf{M}$ is positive definite, the sensitivity on matrix form becomes

$$\frac{d\omega_j}{d\gamma_e} = \frac{1}{2\omega_j} \frac{\mathbf{E}_j^H \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_e} - \omega_j^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_e} \right) \mathbf{E}_j}{\mathbf{E}_j^H \mathbf{M} \mathbf{E}_j} \quad (2.4.7)$$

The full derivation can be found in Appendix C.2. It should be noted that it is not assumed that the eigenmodes are mass-normalized. Furthermore it is seen, contrary to many other topology optimization problems, that no adjoint equation needs to be solved in order to determine the sensitivities [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. Only the matrices $\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_e}$ and $\frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_e}$ are needed, and for the problem of designing photonic crystals the matrix $\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_e} = \mathbf{0}$ since the permeability is considered to be constant.

The sensitivity of the objective function can then, using the assumption that $f(\boldsymbol{\gamma})$ is smooth, be stated as

$$\frac{df}{d\gamma_i} = 4 \frac{\max_k \omega_j^k \frac{d}{d\gamma_i} \left(\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k \right) - \min_k \omega_{j+1}^k \frac{d}{d\gamma_i} \left(\max_k \omega_j^k \right)}{\left[\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k + \max_k \omega_j^k \right]^2} \quad (2.4.8)$$

and similarly for the constraints, e.g. $g(x) = \min_k \omega_{j+1}^k - \omega_{j+1}^k \leq 0$.

$$\frac{dg}{d\gamma_i} = \frac{d}{d\gamma_i} \left(\min_k \omega_{j+1}^k \right) - \frac{d}{d\gamma_i} \left(\omega_{j+1}^k \right) \quad (2.4.9)$$

When reducing the design space using symmetry considerations as described in Section 2.2, the sensitivities must be updated appropriately. This is a consequence of the eigenmodes not necessarily will take on the same symmetry as the design. To take this into account the sensitivity of a given γ_j in the reduced design space, must be a sum over all other γ_i in the full design, i.e.

$$\frac{d\tilde{\omega}}{d\gamma_j} = \sum_i^N \frac{d\omega}{d\gamma_i} N_i^\omega \quad (2.4.10)$$

where N is the number of design variables in the full design and N^ω is a vector which is one when γ_i is symmetric to γ_j and zero elsewhere.

Finally one should note that multiple eigenvalues may ruin the above stated sensitivity analysis, since it has its basis in the assumption of the eigenpairs being distinct. To remedy this possible problem the method presented in [Seyranian et al., 1994] and [Pedersen, 2006] is used to compute sensitivities of multiple eigenvalues, see Appendix C.3 for details of the method.

2.5 Summary of Photonic Band Gap Optimization

Maxwell's EVP along with the Bloch wave representation have been presented together with its FE discretization.

The basic physics and methods for interpreting the optical properties of a photonic crystal, such as the band structure as well as an intuitive understanding of the origin of band gaps have been introduced. To shed light on the modeling aspects, the crystal lattice and reciprocal lattice are presented, which together with symmetry considerations lead to the concept of the irreducible Brillouin zone.

The standard framework of topology optimization is applied to formulate a design problem with the objective of maximizing band gaps in photonic crystals. The optimization problem utilizes an active set strategy and empirical knowledge to pose the design task as a "smooth" optimization problem. The optimization problem was seen to be non-linear and non-convex, which means that it is not possible to identify a global minimum, i.e. the KKT conditions only ensure local optimality. The solution of the optimization problem is to be determined using a gradient based optimization algorithm, i.e. the method of moving asymptotes by K. Svanberg [Svanberg, 1987], and the chapter is therefore concluded by a presentation of the sensitivity analysis.

Implementation and Verification

The discrete FE equations, eqs. (2.3.1), are implemented in the commercial FE-package COMSOL Multiphysics 3.3a [COMSOL, 2007]. COMSOL has, besides a Graphical User Interface (GUI), a high level scripting language associated with it, which can be used in conjunction with Matlab. This combination is used throughout the implementation, such that Matlab functions can be called, e.g. the MMA algorithm. For verification purposes the EVP is also implemented from scratch in Matlab. However, this implementation is limited to very small scale problems, i.e. coarse mesh resolutions. The general flowchart for the optimization programme, which is the same for both the Matlab and COMSOL implementations, is shown in Fig. 3.1.

Figure 3.1: Flowchart for the optimization programme.

All computations have been performed on a shared memory Linux system with eight AMD 64 bit 2200 MHz CPUs and a total of 16GB memory unless otherwise stated.

3.1 Setting Up and Solving the EVP

The eigenvalue problem is set up in COMSOL using the weak form of the PDEs. This is easily done since COMSOL has a weak form scripting interface, that is based on variational calculus. Thus the EVP can be entered into COMSOL in a very intuitive manner, see Appendix H.1. The Bloch periodic Dirichlet conditions are on the other hand not that easily implemented, c.f. that the Dirichlet conditions are not natural to the weak form, and are therefore implemented using the COMSOL GUI¹.

The choice of element shape function order, for approximation of $\mathbf{E}$ and ψ , is based on the discrete optimization problem. Since the design resolution is of utmost importance, and only one design variable exists per element in the mesh, first order edge-elements are used for $\mathbf{E}$ and first order Lagrange elements for ψ . This results in the lowest possible number of degrees of freedom in the linear equations, i.e. faster solution time.

The mesh is also restricted to solely consist of brick elements, since this makes the symmetry mappings easier to derive.

The resulting algebraic EVP, eq. (2.3.3), is finally solved using COMSOL's build-in eigenvalue solver `femeig`. This is a Krylov subspace based Arnoldi algorithm, which iterates over a subspace of approximate eigenvectors until convergence is met [Zhu and Cangellaris, 2006]. To speed up convergence a shift value can be given, which in this paper is set to 0.1. This value has been chosen since linearity of the EVP has been utilized to set the length scale to unity instead of nanometers. This results in frequencies in the order of magnitude 10^0 Hz, as opposed to a magnitude of 10^{12-15} Hz when using the real dimensions. In each loop of the Arnoldi scheme a system of linear equations needs to be solved. COMSOL has many possible solvers available, but unless otherwise stated the `pardiso` direct solver has been used throughout the thesis. When using an iterative method for solving the EVP, one should be aware that the solver might not converge to the desired number of eigenvalues. Therefore the solver script is extended with a secondary solver call, which call `femeig` with a larger subspace and thereby curing this problem.

Another aspect of solving the linear EVP, comes from the Bloch periodic BCs. At high symmetry points many eigenvalues are likely to be multiple, c.f. Fig. 2.8. This slows down the convergence of the Arnoldi process [Zhu and Cangellaris, 2006], and might even prevent it in converging to the desired number of eigenvalues. To remedy this potential problem, all high symmetry point are shifted by 10^{-2} from their true value.

¹The method COMSOL uses to implement periodic BCs is not clear to the author, and through correspondence with their support section, it has been understood, that this is a matter which will be remedied in the upcoming version of COMSOL.

Figure 3.2: Plot of the speedup effect, $S(P) = \frac{T(1)}{T(P)}$, for $P = 1, \dots, 7$ CPUs, based on the computation of the first 10 eigenvalues for seven entries in the wave vector using the photonic crystal in Figure 2.7 as test case. It is seen that linear speedup is not achieved, which is contributed to the fact that seven EVPs solved simultaneously on seven CPUs, only can be solved as fast as the slowest problem allows, i.e. the EVP at the high symmetry point Γ acts as a bottleneck.

3.1.1 Parallelization

Due to the Bloch wave representation of the electric field, each optimization iteration involves the solution of several EVPs, i.e. one for each entry in the wave-vector. Since these EVPs are uncoupled the problem falls into the category of embarrassingly parallel problems. This property is utilized by adopting a platform independent multicore Matlab script written by M.Buehren [Buehren, 2007] into the state problem solver, see Appendix H.2.

The parallelization program consists of two main components. First the master script creates a directory in which it writes one parameter file for each wave vector entry. The second key component is a slave script. One slave script is to be executed for each extra CPU wanted, i.e. each extra processor requires an extra license to both COMSOL and Matlab. The number of licences is not a problem. However, on the AMD system at hand, a maximum of seven slave CPUs are possible. Note that the total memory available can reduce this number if a given discretization requires more than 2 GB memory per EVP.

In order to quantify the effect of the parallel solution method, the following investigation is performed. For three different mesh resolutions, one complete optimization iteration is performed with seven entries in the wave vector, solved for the first 10 eigenvalues. By measuring the time spend, the effective speedup can

Mesh	ω_0	error [%]
$8 \times 8 \times 8$	0.4625	2.75 %
$16 \times 16 \times 16$	0.4513	0.26 %
$24 \times 24 \times 24$	0.4498	0.07 %

Table 3.1: Error between eigenvalues computed using the COMSOL implementation and the (finite difference) numerical result given in [Chern et al., 2007]. The comparison is based on the center frequency which in [Chern et al., 2007] was found to be $\omega_0 = 0.4501$ for the photonic crystal in shown Figure 3.3.

be expressed by the following ratio

$$S(P) = \frac{T(1)}{T(P)} \quad (3.1.1)$$

where S is the speedup, P is the number of processors and T is computation time. The investigation is based on the scaffold photonic crystal in Figure 2.7 and the results are shown in Figure 3.2.

From Figure 3.2 it is observed that linear (ideal) speedup is not achieved. However it is seen that the denser the mesh, the better the speedup gets. Since the problem is embarrassingly parallel one could have hoped for better results. Therefore an extra investigation of the different entries in the wave vector was performed. This showed that the bottleneck is the high symmetry point Γ . The reason why Γ is a specially problematic high symmetry point, can be seen in Figure 2.7, where it is seen that Γ contains the largest concentration of multiple eigenvalues. Thus the speedup analysis simply showed that seven EVPs solved simultaneously on seven CPUs, only can be solved as fast as the slowest problem allows. Therefore the speedup analysis should have been performed on a finer discretized wave vector, such that the number of EVPs exceeds the number of CPUs at hand. Due to time issues this analysis has not been performed in full. Instead a simplified analysis was made in which the EVP was solved for 22 entries in the wave vector on a mesh of $24 \times 24 \times 24$ elements. The EVPs was first solved on one CPU, which took 230 minutes, and then using 7 CPUs which took 40 minutes. This showed a speedup of $S(7) = 5.75$ which is much better than the $S(7) = 3.5$ in Figure 3.2.

3.1.2 Convergence of EV solver

In order to validate that Maxwell's EVP with Bloch boundary conditions have been implemented correctly, the convergence of the eigenvalues have been compared to results from [Chern et al., 2007]. The test case is the sc photonic crystal shown in Figure 3.3. The comparison is based on the center frequency of the photonic band

Figure 3.3: Band diagram (left) and unit cell (right) of the sc photonic crystal used for the convergence analysis. The radii of the spheres and cylinders are $r_s = 0.345a$ and $r_c = 0.11a$ respectively, and the dielectric contrast is $\epsilon_2/\epsilon_1 = 13$. This structure has a band gap of 13.6 % between the fifth and sixth bands [Chern et al., 2007].

gap between bands five and six, i.e.

$$\omega_0 = \frac{1}{2} \left(\min_k \omega_6^k + \max_k \omega_5^k \right) \quad (3.1.2)$$

In [Chern et al., 2007] the center frequency was found to be $\omega_0 = 0.4501$ using finite differences computed on a $48 \times 48 \times 48$ mesh. In table 3.1 the COMSOL solution is given for three different meshes, and it is seen that a mesh of $16 \times 16 \times 16$ gives rise to an error of less than 1%. Thus it can be concluded that the COMSOL implementation of Maxwell’s EVP with Bloch boundary conditions is correct.

3.1.3 CPU time

The main computational burden when optimization 3D design problems, is the solution of the state equations. This is also the case for modelling 3D photonic crystals and this section is therefore devoted to the investigation of CPU time and memory usage as well as convergence of eigenvalues.

A key issue when performing 3D simulations is the required CPU time. That is, how long time does it take to solve the state equations. This is of special interest since a higher mesh resolution provides for finer details in the design, but also larger linear system of equations. Therefore a simple profiling of the optimization programme is performed. The red graph in Fig. 3.4 shows the total time for one optimization iteration, i.e. EVP, sensitivity analysis and design update, and the

Figure 3.4: CPU time for one optimization iteration as a function of elements in the FE mesh, computed for one wave vector entry, $\mathbf{k} = \Gamma$, for the first 10 eigenvalues. The code has been executed sequentially and the blue curve refers to the EVP alone, while the red curve also includes sensitivity analysis and design update.

blue curve shows how much time is spend on solving one state problem, for a number of different meshes. Only the high symmetry point Γ is included, since this point has been seen to be the bottleneck, i.e. no parallelization is utilized, and the active set is chosen to be of size $M = 4$.

It is found that the solution time for a mesh of 24^3 elements takes approximately 20 minutes and allocates approximately 1.7 GB of memory. It is also seen that for an active set of size $M = 4$, the solution of the state problem makes up approximately 90 % of the total iteration time.

Regarding the overall CPU time it is clear that in order to solve problems with even finer meshing, alternative solution methods should be considered. For example combining the Arnoldi scheme with a multigrid linear solver as in [Zhu and Cangellaris, 2006], or perhaps severely lowering the tolerances for eigenvalue convergence and still use a direct solver. However, direct solvers have a limit based on their memory usage, thus making the obvious choice an iterative linear solver. Unfortunately COMSOL does not have working version of such an iterative solver, capable of solving the semi-definite problem in Maxwell’s EVP.

3.1.4 Edge Elements

Since edge-elements differ from the standard nodal based FE basis functions, this section provides a short description of their most important properties.

The basis function for an edge-element is a vector valued function that takes on unity at a given edge and zero elsewhere. A first order vector basis function for a brick element with sidelength dx , dy and dz , can be stated as follows for the

Figure 3.5: Illustration of how to implement the periodic Bloch BCs using the penalization method [Cook et al., 2002]. $\alpha \gg \max(\mathbf{K})$ is the penalization factor and $\max(\mathbf{K})$ refers to the largest entry in the system matrix.

edge at $y = z = 0$.

$$\mathbf{N}_1^e(\mathbf{x}) = \frac{1}{dydz} (dy - y) (dz - z) \mathbf{e}_x + 0\mathbf{e}_y + 0\mathbf{e}_z \quad (3.1.3)$$

Repeating this for each edge yields a shape function matrix of size 3×12 accompanied by a column vector holding the twelve edge degrees of freedom. It should be noted that the curl of these shape functions are square integrable, i.e. they are part of the discrete $H^h(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ space, and that the divergence of $\mathbf{N}_i^e$ is zero. However since FEM is a global conservation scheme, the zero divergence property does not transfer to the global system and hence the stabilized FE formulation is indeed needed. For the computation of the mass, stiffness and coupling matrices see Appendix F.

3.1.5 Bloch Boundary Conditions

The implementation of periodic BCs in COMSOL is hardly transparent, and therefore a simple example of how the BCs could be implemented is illustrated in Fig. 3.5. This method uses a large penalization parameter, α , to enforce the BCs. The value of α is typically chosen to be $\max(\mathbf{K}) \cdot 10^9$, where $\max(\mathbf{K})$ refers to the largest entry in the system matrix. This method is effective and easy to implement, though it can lead to ill conditioned system matrices, which makes it most suitable for direct solution methods. This method is also used in the Matlab verification program.

3.2 Sensitivities, Design Update and Stopping Criteria

In order to utilize COMSOL for computing the sensitivities, the design variable is included in the FE formulation as an extra dependent variable with an element-wise constant shape function. This, however, poses a small problem with respect to the symmetry mapping operators needed for the sensitivity analysis as well as the

geometry update. These operators have been derived based on special ordering of element center coordinates in the Matlab implementation, and therefore a mapping from COMSOL element numbering to Matlab have had to be constructed. The construction of the necessary symmetry mappings has proven to be one of the most time consuming parts of the implementation process. One should however note that the symmetry mapping operator also could have been determined by searching through element coordinates, using distances and angles as identification parameters. This approach have not been pursued further in the present implementation.

The sensitivity analysis is entered into COMSOL on integral form in total analogy to the form presented in Appendix C.2, and a function that computes the objective and constraint values as well as their sensitivities can be found in Appendix H.3.

The implementation of the multiple eigenvalues sensitivity analysis described in Appendix C.3 requires that a tolerance for determining when two or more eigenvalues can be regarded as multiple. It has been determined that a tolerance of 10^{-5} works very well, i.e. $|\lambda_i - \lambda_j| < 10^{-5}$ the eigenvalues are considered as multiple. The implemented sensitivity analysis can be found in Appendix H.3.

The Matlab implementation of MMA by K. Svanberg [Svanberg, 1998], is called to update the design variables, and the optimization loop is continued until termination by a stopping criteria; $||\gamma^m - \gamma^{m-1}|| < 10^{-2}$ and $|f^m - f^{m-1}| < 10^{-2}$ where m is the iteration counter. Note that the stopping criteria utilizes that $\gamma \in [0, 1]$ and that $f(\gamma)$ is a relative measure. It might also be necessary for the user to stop the optimization process prematurely, if the choice of active set is no longer valid, which can be the case when using the zipper approach.

Due to the CPU time needed to solve finely discretized 3D problems, a routine that maps the design on a coarse mesh to a finer mesh is created. In this way valuable time can be saved in the optimization process. Though this approach can save time, one should be aware that it also can lead to a local minimum already at the coarse mesh, which means that the mesh refinement approach cannot be used without caution. Also to save CPU time, the discretization of the path around the boundaries of the irreducible Brillouin zone is chosen to be as coarse as possible. This, of course, varies from optimization problem to optimization problem as will become clear in Chapter 5 and 6.

3.2.1 Verification of Sensitivities

Validating the implementation of the optimization problem, is done by making sure the sensitivities are computed correct. The sensitivities computed by COMSOL are validated using a forward difference check given by

$$\frac{d\tilde{\omega}_j}{d\gamma_i} \approx \frac{\phi(\gamma + h_i) - \phi(\gamma)}{\|h_i\|} \quad (3.2.1)$$

Figure 3.6: Finite difference check of the COMSOL generated sensitivities as given in eq. (3.2.1) including the symmetry mapping. The five graphs correspond to five different appropriately chosen design variables, and the part of the graph between the vertical lines is seen to display asymptotic convergence, i.e. the sensitivities are correct.

where $h_i \in \mathbb{R}^n$ is a vector with zeroes everywhere, except for the entry corresponding to γ_i where a small positive perturbation dx is placed. Note that the finite difference verification only is performed for the single eigenvalue sensitivity analysis.

In Fig. 3.6 the relative error between the COMSOL result and the finite difference estimation is shown in a double logarithmic plot for five design variables. The computation is based on the scaffold structure in Figure 2.7. The design variables are chosen such that two lies on the boundary of the domain, while the three remaining lies in the interior, but situated such that their symmetry representation are different. It can be seen in Figure 3.6 that between the two red vertical lines, the asymptotic slope is -1 which is in agreement with eq. (3.2.1). Moving further along $dx \rightarrow 0$ it is observed that around $dx = 10^{-6}$ the error starts growing. This is to be expected since numerical problems are known to rise, when the numbers approaches machine precision.

3.3 Visualization of 3D Designs

A common issue when performing 3D simulations is how to visualize the results, such that the essential topologies are clear to the reader without cluttering the thesis with figures. Many different approaches and software packages are available such as the commercial TecPlot and the open-source tool ParaView². However, in this thesis only Matlab and COMSOL plotting tools are utilized. The plotting tools have been devised such that the following two characteristics are fulfilled.

²For details visit www.tecplot.com and www.paraview.org respectively.

First and foremost it is important that the general layout of the optimized design is easily comprehensible to the reader. For this purpose it was found, that a smoothed isosurface representation of the design yielded the desired result. Since the isosurfaces leads to open faces the Matlab function `isocaps` has been applied to close these. Secondly it is imperative to show the discrete nature of the optimized designs, c.f. the FEM and the elementwise constant design variables. This can be achieved using plotting routines build into COMSOL. The latter type of design representation also has the capability of illustrating if a design variable has not converged to the box constraints. This information would be lost if only using the isosurface representation, since the isosurfaces is based on a cutoff value known as the isovalue. On the other hand, the element plots can be difficult to interpret for complex geometries, and this is where the isosurface representation has its strength. Thus, both types of visualizations are found to be necessary, and the implemented functions can be found in Appendix H.4.

Finally there is one more issue to deal with when performing 3D topology optimization. That is, one should always verify that the optimized design does not contain hidden cavities. This can be accomplished using cross sectional plots, which will be displayed if necessary when presenting the optimized design in the following Chapters.

3.4 Summary of Implementation Issues

This chapter showed that the COMSOL implementation of Maxwell's EVP with Bloch boundary conditions was successful, i.e. convergence to results from the literature was found. The nature of Maxwell's EVP with Bloch BCs was utilized to parallelize the solution process, and a maximum speedup of 5.75 was found using 7 CPUs and 22 entries in the wave vector. It was observed that in order to obtain good parallel scaling the number of EVPs should exceed the number of slave CPUs. Moreover several symmetry mapping functions was derived to ensure that e.g. a simple cubic design fulfils the symmetries of the simple cubic lattice, and that the sensitivities are updated accordingly.

The optimization setup was verified by a finite difference check of the sensitivities. This check is adequate since the Matlab implementation of MMA written by K. Svanberg [Svanberg, 1998] works as long as it is provided with the correct sensitivities.

Though the implementation was successful in the sense that correct results are obtained, one major issue remains. The problem, which is general for most 3D simulations, has to do with the relation between FE mesh resolution and the CPU time and memory needed in the solution of the state problem. The COMSOL eigenvalue solver on the Linux AMD system used in this thesis had a limit of $24 \times 24 \times 24 \approx 14000$ elements. Above this mesh density it is no longer possible to use all eight CPUs due to the amount of memory available. Even if extra memory was available the solution time would still pose a problem. With respect

to the design problem, a mesh of 14000 elements is regarded as being coarse. The conclusion is therefore that an iterative linear solver should be included in the eigenvalue solver. As stated earlier, COMSOL cannot accommodate this request at the present time, and though the literature is rich with examples of such solvers, e.g. [Zhu and Cangellaris, 2006, Dobson et al., 2000, Zaglmayr, 2006], these are not simple to implement. Therefore the results presented in the remaining part of this thesis, will be limited to mesh densities as described above.

Preliminary Optimization Results

In this Chapter a simplified test of the complete optimization scheme is presented. The aim is to ensure that optimized designs are in agreement with analytical predictions of the optimal layout of the 1D multi-layer film or Bragg grating.

4.1 Optimization Settings for Bragg Gratings

In this Section the optimization program is applied to the 1D optimization problem of designing the well-known Bragg gratings [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. The analytical result states a relation between the dielectric contrast and the thickness of the different layers, i.e.

$$n_1 d_1 = n_2 d_2 \quad (4.1.1)$$

where $n_i = \sqrt{\mu\epsilon_i}$ is the refractive index [Balanis, 1989] and d_1 and d_2 are the thickness's of the layers corresponding to the dielectrics with refractive index n_1 and n_2 respectively.

Since the multi-layer film only display a one dimensional periodicity as well as a one dimensional band gap, some simplifications of the presented optimization scheme must be made. Restricting the wave vector to only vary between the high symmetry points Γ and X in the sc lattice, is equivalent to considering one dimensional waves with varying periodicity. And contrary to design problems of the sc and fcc crystal lattices, no symmetry requirements on the design is needed. Thus all elements in the unit cube are considered as design variables.

For the study presented in the following Section the wave vector from $\Gamma - X$ is discretized by ten uniformly spaced points, and $2M = 8$ constraints are included in the active set. The initial guess is shown in Figure 4.1a, and is comprised of an air-sphere of radius 0.55 in a dielectric background. The corresponding band diagram is shown in Figure 4.1b for a dielectric contrast of 13, which illustrates that a incomplete band gap is already present between the second and third frequency bands for the partial wave spectrum Γ and X , i.e. no zipper needed. Since the design task is relatively simple, the influence of the initial guess will be postponed to later and more challenging design problems. Finally the optimization problem

(a) Initial guess for the design problem. An air-sphere with radius $0.55a$ in a dielectric (blue) background. The lattice is recognized as the simple cubic unit cell, and the grey surfaces marks the cut planes. The analysis is computed with a dielectric contrast of $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13$, i.e silicon and air, on a $16 \times 16 \times 16$ mesh.

(b) Band diagram for the sc crystal in Figure 4.1a. The red lines illustrates the wave vectors of interest, and the presence of a 35 % 1D gap is noted and shown by the light grey area. The dark grey area above shows the presence of a complete band gap between the fifth and sixth bands of 2.5%.

Figure 4.1: Unit cell consisting of an air-sphere in a dielectric background material (a) and the corresponding band diagram (b).

is solved for two different dielectric contrast, i.e. $\epsilon_2 = \{4, 13\}$ and $\epsilon_1 = 1$, on a $16 \times 16 \times 16$ FE-mesh using eight CPUs.

4.2 Optimized Bragg Gratings

For a dielectric contrast of 4, the relation between the gratings are expected to be $d_1 = 2d_2$, i.e. on the unit cube $d_1 = \frac{2}{3}$ and $d_2 = \frac{1}{3}$. By inspection of Figure 4.2a this is seen to be in good agreement with the analytical prediction. For the second contrast of $\epsilon_2/\epsilon_1 = 13$ the analytic expression states that $d_1 = 3.6d_2$. This is not obvious in Figure 4.2c, where is observed that two rows of elements have not converged to a 0-1 solution. This is most likely due to the coarse mesh used for the modelling, since the mesh cannot capture the dimensions of $d_1 = 0.78$ and $d_2 = 0.22$ when each element has sidelength 0.0625. However, by assuming that intermediate design variables refer to an element thickness proportional to their values, i.e. $\gamma_i = 0.8$ means that 80 % of γ_i is considered to be air, the analytical prediction is seen to be in fair agreement with the optimized design.

The one dimensional gap to midgap ratio for the two optimized designs are found to be 43% and 70.5% for the dielectric contrast of 4 and 13 respectively. This corresponds very well with the theory stating that a larger contrast leads to a larger band gap. This and other optimization data such as iteration history is given

Contrast	Init. design	Mesh	M	$\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0}$	Iter.	Time	Figure
$\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 4$	Figure 4.1a	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	4	0.43	27	≈ 2 h	4.2a
$\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13$	Figure 4.1a	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	4	0.705	73	≈ 7 h	4.2c

Table 4.1: Optimization data for the two Bragg grating optimization problems.

Figure 4.2: Optimized designs (left column) and corresponding band diagram (right column) for the Bragg grating problem.

Figure 4.3: Convergence history for the optimized Bragg grating design with dielectric contrast of 13, c.f. the design in Figure 4.2c. Note that the relative gap is negative on the y-axis due to simple fact that $\max f(\gamma) = \min -f(\gamma)$.

in Table 4.1, where it is also seen that the high contrast design used three times as many iterations to converge as the low contrast design. Again this difference is contributed to the coarse mesh and its inability to resolve the optimal design. A plot of the convergence of the objective function for the high contrast design is shown in Figure 4.3. From Figure 4.3 it is seen that the optimization scheme converges almost monotonically towards the optimum, though a small kink is seen around iterations 20 to 23. It should also be noted that though the objective function attains in minimum after approximately 15 iterations, it still takes over 50 extra iterations for the design change to go beneath the 1 % allowed by the stopping criteria, c.f. Section 3.2.

The Bragg grating optimization results showed how the COMSOL implementation can be used to design 1D photonic crystals in good agreement with analytical predictions.

4.3 Influence of the size of the Active Set

This section investigates what happens with the convergence, optimized design and objective function when using different sizes of active set, i.e. different values of M . The general problem setting is as stated in Section 4.1, though only the case of a high dielectric contrast is examined, i.e. $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13$.

Two examples are studied, one where the active set is small, i.e. $M = 1$, and one where the active set is large, i.e. $M = 20$. The latter has been chosen such that all eigenvalues of the lower part of the band diagram are included, c.f. the wave vector discretization.

In Figure 4.4 the resulting designs and corresponding convergence history is shown.

(a) Optimized design for $M = 1$. Terminated by user after 86 iterations.

(b) Convergence history for $M = 1$. Oscillations are seen, not only in the early iterations, and therefore the optimization is terminated after 86 iterations.

(c) Optimized design for $M = 20$. The design is seen to be qualitatively equivalent to that of Figure 4.2c.

(d) Convergence history for $M = 20$. The optimization problem is seen to converge monotonically.

Figure 4.4: Illustrations of the influence of the size of the active set with respect to convergence properties and optimized designs.

(a) Shift in indices of the objective function versus number of iterations for $M = 1$.

(b) Shift in indices of the objective function versus number of iterations for $M = 20$.

Figure 4.5: Illustration of how many times the indices of the objective function shifts during the optimization process. Each jump between one and two corresponds to a shift in either the upper or lower index of the objective function.

From Figure 4.4 it is clear that choosing M too small results in an oscillatory convergence history. This is not desired, since it makes the application of the stopping criteria from Section 3.2 less reliable. In fact, after 86 iterations with $M = 1$ the design change was still over 20 %, and therefore the job was terminated.

It is also noticed that the two cases yields qualitatively the same designs, with almost equal objective values. However, this does not affect the problem regarding the fulfillment of the stopping criteria, and thus it is crucial that M is chosen appropriately, i.e. not too small, due to the reasons described above, but also not too large, since it is seen that for $M = 20$, it takes 112 iterations to converge while $M = 4$ converges in 73 iterations.

4.3.1 Smoothness of the Optimization Problem

The optimization problem $(P)_1$ is clearly non-smooth due to nature of the objective function. It is however attacked as a smooth problem and therefore it is interesting to see if this assumption holds. To check this assumption the two examples presented in the previous section are used. For each iteration it is examined whether or not the indices of the objective change and the result is plotted in Figure 4.5.

From Figure 4.5 it is seen that neither of the two active set strategies yields a smooth problem, i.e. both problems experience jumps in the objective indices.

For the case of a small active set, i.e. $M = 1$, the jumps in the objective indices are very pronounced. And by comparison with the converge plot in Figure 4.4b it is seen that the jumps in objective indices also leads to jumps in the convergence of the objective function.

The case with $M = 20$ also contains jumps in the objective indices, though they

(a) Optimized design on a $16 \times 16 \times 16$ mesh with $M = 4$ and a dielectric contrast of 13.

(b) Convergence history for the design in Figure 4.6a.

Figure 4.6: Optimized Bragg gratings determined by the bound formulation, c.f. Appendix C.1

are more sparsely distributed than for $M = 1$. A comparison to the convergence history of Figure 4.4d reveals that the non-smoothness does not seem to pose a problem with respect to reaching a local minimum. So even though the problem $(P)_1$ is non-smooth, its convergence properties indicate that it can be used for the optimization of photonic crystals.

4.4 Comparison to the Bound Formulation

In continuation of the previous Section a small comparison between the convergence properties and optimized design for the bound formulation of Appendix C.1 and $(P)_1$ is performed. The example problem is the Bragg grating problem with a dielectric contrast of 13, and all optimization settings are kept as given in introduction to this Chapter. The result of the optimization process is given in Figure 4.6.

From Figure 4.6 it is seen that there is a clear difference between the optimized design produced by the bound formulation and $(P)_1$. The optimized design in Figure 4.6a is seen to have converged to an almost pure 0-1 design. However, by measuring the thicknesses d_1 and d_2 one finds that $d_1 \approx 0.87$ and $d_2 \approx 0.13$ which does not correspond to the analytical prediction of $d_1 = 0.78$ and $d_2 = 0.22$. Also it is seen that the band gap is 66.5 % which is less than the objective obtained by using $(P)_1$. Thus, the minimum attained is a local minimum. Regarding the convergence history it is observed from Figure 4.6b that though the bound formulation converges in 47 iterations, apposed to 73 for $(P)_1$, the curve is not monotonically decreasing.

As to why the bound formulation reaches a different minimum than $(P)_1$ is not understood by the author. Though a qualified guess would be that the objective function in the bound formulation lack information of the underlying problem, i.e.

the frequencies do not enter in the objective function. The opposite is the case in $(P)_1$, which may provide the MMA optimizer with extra and apparently useful information. Also discussions with the thesis supervisors have contributed to the choice of using the "semi-smooth" optimization problem $(P)_1$ as a basis for the optimization of photonic crystals.

4.5 Summary of the Preliminary Tests

The preliminary optimization test have shown that the implemented optimization problem. $(P)_1$, works and can produce the basic 1D photonic crystal of Bragg gratings.

It was seen that the optimized designs was in good agreement with analytical predictions, and that a higher dielectric contrast yields a larger band gap.

By comparing the semi-smooth optimization problem $(P)_1$ to the smooth bound formulation presented in Appendix C.1, it was found that $(P)_1$ in fact returned the optimized design which was in best agreement with the analytical prediction. This was contributed to the fact that the objective in $(P)_1$ contains information of the underlying physics. The opposite is the case for the bound formulation which has two artificial variables in the objective function. Thus, the optimization problem $(P)_1$ was found to be the best candidate for photonic crystal optimization, though it lacks mathematical proof of smoothness.

Finally the size of the active set was seen to be crucial for the convergence properties of the scheme, i.e. if M was chosen too small the objective function oscillates and if chosen too large it slows down convergence.

Optimized Designs for the sc Lattice

The design of 3D photonic crystals is in this chapter examined for the simple cubic lattice. Before the results are presented the general framework under which the optimization is performed is introduced.

An important issue in 3D band gap optimization is that it might not be possible to open any arbitrary gap. For example a complete band gap between bands one and two has never been shown to exist, c.f. [Sözüer and Haus, 1993] and [Dobson et al., 2000]. This specific case can be explained by the common fact that the first two bands start at zero, i.e. $\omega_1(\Gamma) = \omega_2(\Gamma) = 0$. And furthermore that the two modes corresponding to the first two frequency bands corresponds to a TE and TM mode respectively [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. Therefore only gaps which have been shown to exist in the literature are investigated.

When optimizing sc crystals using only the wave spectrum of the irreducible Brillouin zone for the sc lattice, it is of utmost importance that the optimized designs fulfil the symmetry requirements of the sc lattice. Using that the sc lattice has nine mirror-symmetry planes in the unit cube, [Kittel, 1996], the active design

Figure 5.1: Illustration of the active design variables upon restricting the design to fulfil the sc mirror symmetry. Based on a $10 \times 10 \times 10$ mesh this leads to 35 active variables.

variables are reduced to 1/48 plus interfaces of the total number of elements. In Figure 5.1 the active design variables of the sc lattice is shown.

From Figure 5.1 it is seen that a mesh of 1000 elements leads to 35 active design variables, and furthermore it is observed that the geometry of the active variables is identical to that of the sc irreducible Brillouin zone. It is also this symmetry operator that is used for the sensitivity update in eq. (2.4.10).

The results presented next are all based on a dielectric material with $\epsilon_2 = 13$, i.e. silicon, in a air filled background, i.e. $\epsilon_1 = 1$. Both are non-magnetic and have a constant permeability of 1. This choice is consistent with results presented in the literature, e.g. [Dobson et al., 2000, Maldovan and Thomas, 2004, Joannopoulos et al., 1995], and thereby makes it possible to compare the relative band gap sizes.

As a consequence of the difficulties associated with illustrating 3D geometries, all optimized 3D designs can be found as Matlab Figure files on the CD accompanying this thesis, c.f. Appendix G. For simplicity the Matlab figures have been named according to the numbering, e.g. Figure 5.2b is named `Figure_5_2b.fig` on the CD.

5.1 Known sc Photonic Band Gap Crystals

The sc lattice has, due to its simplicity with respect to the first Brillouin zone and the design symmetries, been studied extensively in the literature, e.g. [Sözüer and Haus, 1993], [Dobson et al., 2000] and [Chern et al., 2007]. These studies concerns both modelling issues, fabrication problems as well as parameter studies of the optimal dimensions.

In these papers it is found that two general classes of sc photonic band gap crystals with complete band gaps exists. The first class displays a complete band gap between the second and third bands, while the other class displays the gap between the fifth and sixth bands.

From the first class we find the rectangular scaffold structure as seen in Figure 2.7 which has a complete gap of approximately 7%. Studies have also been made where the rectangular rods are replaced by circular rods, which lead to approximately the same size band gap, see [Sözüer and Haus, 1993].

From the second class of sc crystals we find both the overlapping air-sphere crystal as seen in Figure 4.1a, as well as the sc atomic inspired structure as seen in Figure 3.3. They both exhibit complete band gaps between the fifth and sixth bands. In [Sözüer and Haus, 1993] and [Chern et al., 2007] these structures are optimized by a simple parameter sweep and the gaps are found to be 7 % for an air-sphere of radius $0.7a$ and 13.6 % for the sc atomic-like structure with dimensions as given in Figure 3.3. The atomic inspired design is in fact the sc photonic crystal with the largest reported band gap, c.f. [Chern et al., 2007]. Also note that for an air-sphere of radius $0.55a$ the gap between the fifth and sixth bands is reduced to $\approx 2.5\%$, while a gap between the second and third bands is almost present c.f.

Figure 4.1. This makes the design well-suited as initial guess for both classes of sc photonic crystals.

The reader is referred to e.g. [Sözüer and Haus, 1993] and [Chern et al., 2007] for more examples of sc photonic crystals.

5.2 Gap between the second and third bands

The goal of this optimization problem is to maximize the gap between the second and third band of sc lattice. The optimization was performed based on a 20 point uniform discretization of the wave vector and in each EVP 6 eigenvalues was sought. To shorten the needed CPU time the continuation approach is applied. This means that the optimization is first solved on a coarse mesh, and then the mesh is refined until memory and time becomes a barrier.

As initial guess for the design process, the air-sphere from Figure 4.1a is used. This design does not possess a complete band gap between the second and third bands, and therefore the zipper approach is applied. In Table 5.1 the data from the design process using the air sphere starting guess is collected. Each step in the Table 5.1 corresponds to a new choice of wave vectors for the possible active set $\tilde{K}$ and/or a finer mesh. The optimized design is visualized by smoothed isosurfaces in Figure 5.2, which shows both a single unit cell as well as a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ patch of unit cells, and in Figure 5.3 where the discrete nature of the optimized design can be seen. Finally a band diagram with a fine discretization of the path around the irreducible Brillouin zone, i.e. 50 uniformly spaced points, is plotted in Figure 5.4a.

From Table 5.1 it is observed that the objective at the end of step 1 has almost the same value as the rectangular scaffold design, c.f. Figure 2.8a. A qualitative comparison of this intermediate design also shows a high similarity with the scaffold design of Figure 2.7. It should be noted that step 3 was first performed on a mesh of $24 \times 24 \times 24$ elements. This resulted in a decrease in the objective and therefore the third step was re-analyzed using a finer mesh as stated in Table 5.1. Finally it is seen that the optimized design has improved 21 % compared to that of the rectangular scaffold structure in Figure 2.7, i.e. from 7% to 8.5%. The filling ratio of the optimized design is $\beta = 0.21$.

	Initial design	Procedure	Mesh	M	Relative gap	Iter.
Step 0	Figure 4.1a	Zipper: $\Gamma - X$	$8 \times 8 \times 8$	4	0.065	51
Step 1	From step 0	Normal	$8 \times 8 \times 8$	8	0.071	19
Step 2	From step 1	Normal	$14 \times 14 \times 14$	8	0.078	34
Step 3	From step 2	Normal	$28 \times 28 \times 28$	8	0.085	31

Table 5.1: Design process for the optimization of the gap between band two and three. The total computation time was approx. 42 hours and the optimized design can be found in Figures 5.2 and 5.3 while the band diagram is shown in Figure 5.4a.

(a) Isosurface of a single unit cell. (b) Patch of $2 \times 2 \times 2$ unit cells.

Figure 5.2: Isosurface plots of the design after step 3 with isovalue of 0.9, where the grey indicates cut planes. The crystal has a complete photonic band gap of 8.5 %.

(a) Element plot of design variables greater than 0.5.

(b) Plot of the cube surface.

Figure 5.3: Plot of design variables greater than 0.5 (right) and a surface plot (left) of the optimized design presented in step 3 of Table 5.1. The crystal has a complete photonic band gap of 8.5 %, and was computed on a mesh of $28 \times 28 \times 28$ elements.

Figure 5.4: Band diagram and zoom of the rounded corners for the optimized design in Figure 5.2 and 5.3.

The optimized design shown in Figure 5.2 and 5.3 is seen to be a blend of the rectangular and circular scaffold structure with rounded corners. A zoom of the corner is given in Figure 5.4b for clarification. It should be noted that the optimized design has no hidden cavities and thus making the isosurface plots adequate as illustrations of the design. It is observed that the design consists of connected regions of ϵ_2 -material, i.e. there is no ϵ_2 -material suspended in free air. Finally it is evident that this design is more complicated from a fabrication point of view, than the rectangular scaffold structure.

From the band diagram in Figure 5.4a it is observed that the critical points in the Brillouin zone coincides with the high symmetry points R and X .

This optimization problem have also shown that a finer mesh yields a better objective value, c.f. Table 5.1. This is of cause due to the increase in active design variables on a finer mesh, which in turn provides the optimizer with more manoeuvrability. This emphasizes the need for a faster and better algebraic EVP solver. Moreover the design problem have illustrated that the optimization problem, $(P)_1$, can be used to design 3D photonic band gap crystals.

5.2.1 Influence of the Initial Design

To examine if the optimized design presented in the previous Section was a poor local minimum a small study of varying the initial guess is performed. Here poor refers to the possibility of a small change in initial guess would lead to a new design with larger band gap.

First, a simple test where the rectangular scaffold structure is used as start guess is analyzed. This however lead to the *exact* same design as in Figure 5.2 as well as an almost identical optimization process to that in Table 5.1 continued from step 1.

Therefore another initial guess is generated which again consist of an air-sphere

(a) Isosurface of the optimized design with an isovalue of 0.9. (b) Convergence history of the design shown to the left.

Figure 5.5: Optimized design and convergence history based on an initial guess consisting of an air-sphere with radius $0.48a$ computed on a $28 \times 28 \times 28$ grid. The design has a 8.54% complete band gap between the second and third bands.

in a dielectric background. However instead of having overlapping spheres the radius is set to $0.48a$ on a mesh of $28 \times 28 \times 28$ elements, i.e. one row of elements prevent the air-spheres from overlapping. Due to the fine mesh, the optimization is performed on the a system consisting of $2 \times$ Dual Core Xeon 3.0GHz, i.e. four CPUs, with 16 GB of memory. Since this setup half's the number of CPUs compared to the standard system, the wave vector is discretized in ten uniformly spaced points in order to speed up the optimization process. Note that even though this initial guess does not display a band gap, the optimization was performed without the application of the zipper method. The resulting optimized design and convergence history is shown in Figure 5.5.

From Figure 5.5 it can be seen that the design is qualitatively the same as the one presented in Section 5.2. Moreover it is noted that the objective value, found to be 0.0854, is comparable to that found in Table 5.1. This small analysis have shown that the optimizer returns the same local minimum for all three tested initial guesses.

5.3 Gap between the fifth and sixth bands

In this Section the optimization programme is used to determine an optimized design with a complete band gap between the fifth and sixth frequency bands of the sc irreducible Brillouin zone. The optimization is performed based on a 20 point discretization of the wave vector and the EVPs are solved for the first 10 eigenvalues. In order to save time the continuation approach is applied. The details of the optimization process is collected in Table 5.2.

As initial guess for the optimization process, the air-sphere design from Figure 4.1 is used, due to reasons described in the beginning of this Chapter. From the data shown in Table 5.2 it is seen that the final optimized design has a band gap of 16.6% which is 22% larger than the atomic-inspired design published in [Chern et al., 2007] which has a band gap of 13.6%, c.f. Figure 3.3 for illustration. The filling ratio of the optimized design is $\beta = 0.19$, and it is again seen that the ϵ_2 regions are connected. However, the increase in band gap size does not come for free. This is seen by inspecting the optimized design in Figures 5.6 and 5.7. From

	Initial design	Procedure	Mesh	M	Relative gap	Iter.
Step 0	Figure 4.1	Normal	$8 \times 8 \times 8$	8	0.115	47
Step 1	Design from step 0	Normal	$14 \times 14 \times 14$	8	0.149	59
Step 2	Design from step 1	Normal	$24 \times 24 \times 24$	8	0.166	33

Table 5.2: Details of the design process for optimizing the band gap between the fifth and sixth bands. The optimized design is shown in Figures 5.6 and 5.7 and the band diagram is seen in Figure 5.8. The process took approximately 40 hours to finish.

(a) Isosurface plot of a single unit cell.

(b) Isosurface plot of a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ unit cells.

Figure 5.6: Isosurface plots, with isovalue 0.9, of the sc optimized design with an 16.6% band gap between the fifth and the sixth frequency bands. The details of the design process is collected in Table 5.2.

(a) Element plot of design variables greater than 0.5.

(b) Surface plot of the optimized design.

Figure 5.7: Element (left) and surface (right) plot of the optimized design on computed on a $24 \times 24 \times 24$ mesh with a 16.6% band gap, c.f Table 5.2.

Figure 5.8: Band diagram for the optimized design in Figures 5.6 and 5.7. A complete band gap between the fifth and sixth bands of 16.6% is illustrated by the grey rectangle.

these Figures it is observed that the optimized design is similar to the sc atomic-like structure of Figure 3.3, i.e. dielectric spheres at the lattice points connected by thin cylinders. It is however seen that the optimized design contains an extra air-sphere at each corner. Thus the optimized design is surely more complicated to fabricate than the one proposed by [Chern et al., 2007].

From the band diagram shown in Figure 5.8 one finds that the critical points in the reduced Brillouin zone coincide with the high symmetry points R , X and M .

Finally it should be noted that the same design was obtained when using the atomic like structure from Figure 3.3 as initial guess.

5.3.1 Simplified Parameter Study

The optimized design obtained in the previous section was found to be very similar to the atomic-like structure seen in Figure 3.3 and [Chern et al., 2007]. For clarity the design is reproduced in Figure 5.9a. Therefore it is found to be reasonable to perform a parameter study of the atomic-like structure.

The analysis is performed on a mesh of $18 \times 18 \times 18$ elements and is conducted by computing the band gap for varying sphere and cylinder radii. The result is a response surface and the contour lines of this is plotted in Figure 5.9b.

From Figure 5.9b it is seen that the optimal ratio between sphere radius and cylinder is approximately $\frac{r_s}{r_c} = \frac{0.32}{0.12}$ which yields a relative gap of 13.2%. This result is in good agreement with the design presented in [Chern et al., 2007], where the optimal ratio was found to be $\frac{r_s}{r_c} = \frac{0.345}{0.11}$ and $\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0} = 13.6\%$. The discrepancy is most likely due to the coarse mesh used for the parameter study presented in Figure 5.9b.

Figure 5.9: For the parameter study a FE-mesh of $18 \times 18 \times 18$ elements is used and the dielectric contrast is set to $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13$.

5.4 Scaling study

The final analysis to be performed on the simple cubic lattice, concerns the linearity of Maxwell's EVP. To exemplify that the problem does not have a fundamental lengthscale, the simple design of an air-sphere in a dielectric background media is used.

Two models are analyzed, where the first model consists of a single air-sphere with radius $0.6a$ and the second model has eight air-spheres each with radius $0.3a$. Note that these radii are not optimal, c.f. [Sözüer and Haus, 1993]. The second model is chosen such that it is equivalent to scaling first model by a factor $s = \frac{1}{2}$. According to the relations presented in Section 2.1.1, this should then lead to a scaling of the frequencies by $\tilde{\omega} = \omega/s = 2\omega$.

To ensure that the two analysis are comparable, the single air-sphere model is solved on a $12 \times 12 \times 12$ mesh while the eight air-sphere model is solved on a $24 \times 24 \times 24$ mesh. The analysis is conducted based on a seven point discretization of the wave vector. This reduction is based on the findings regarding high symmetry points in the previous Sections. Finally the first model is solved for the first ten eigenvalues, while the second model is solved for the first 48 for reasons that will become clear soon.

From the two band structures in Figure 5.10 it is first and foremost seen that the band gaps are not situated between the same bands. For the single air sphere the gap lies between the fifth and sixth bands, while the eight sphere crystals displays a gap between the 40th and 41st bands. This is contributed to the fact that the second model contains eight replicas of the single air sphere model, and thereby shifts the band gap location by a factor eighth, i.e. $5 \times 8 = 40$.

Regarding the size of the band gaps a 4% discrepancy is seen to be present, i.e. a 6.81% band gap for the single air sphere and a 7.08% band gap for the eight sphere model. This discrepancy is also visible in the comparison of the center frequencies. The prediction states that the eight sphere model should have a center frequency of $\tilde{\omega}_0 = 0.96$, though it is found to be $\tilde{\omega}_0 = 0.915$, i.e. a 5% discrepancy. Since the FE-meshes were chosen to be identical a zero percent discrepancy was expected. However a 4-5% discrepancy is considered to be an acceptable error with respect to the purpose of this analysis, i.e. to demonstrate the scaling properties of Maxwell's EVP and to illustrate the rise in gap indices when modelling several unit cells within the unit cube.

Finally it should be emphasized that the eight sphere model also reveals a significant computational issue, which has to do with the iterative eigenvalue solver. First of all it takes more iterations, and thereby time, for the Arnoldi scheme to find 50 eigenpairs apposed to 10. And what may be even worse is that the iterative eigensolver can loose accuracy when searching a large subspace with many coinciding eigenvalues [Zaglmayr, 2006]. Though this might be the source for the discrepancies seen in the scaling analysis, the matter has not been further investigated and therefore no conclusion can be drawn.

(a) Photonic crystal of a single overlapping air sphere of radius $0.6a$ in the sc lattice. Computed on a $12 \times 12 \times 12$ mesh with $\frac{\omega_0}{\epsilon_1} = 13$ for the first 10 eigenvalues.

(b) Band structure for the design in Figure 5.10a which displays a 6.81 % gap between the fifth and sixth bands. The centerfrequency is found to be $\omega_0 = 0.48$.

(c) Photonic crystal of eight overlapping air sphere of radius $0.3a$ in the sc lattice. Computed on a $24 \times 24 \times 24$ mesh with $\frac{\omega_0}{\epsilon_1} = 13$ for the first 48 eigenvalues.

(d) Band structure for the design in Figure 5.10c which displays a 7.08 % gap between the 40th and 41st bands. The centerfrequency is found to be $\omega_0 = 0.915$.

Figure 5.10: Photonic crystals and the corresponding band diagrams used for the scaling study. The design in Figure 5.10a is chosen to be a factor $s = 2$ times larger than the design in Figure 5.10c.

5.4.1 Scaling the Dielectric Function

This Section examines what happens to the optimized design when the high dielectric material is changed, i.e. setting $\epsilon_2 = 13.6$ apposed to $\epsilon_2 = 13$. The optimization is again based on the overlapping air sphere design in Figure 4.1, and the analysis is performed using the continuation approach such that the final design has a resolution of $24 \times 24 \times 24$ elements.

The optimized design can be seen in Figures 5.11 and 5.12b, while the band diagram is displayed in Figure 5.12a. It is first observed that the minute change in dielectric contrast yields a band gap of 17.7% between the fifth and sixth bands. This is 1.1% larger than the band gap of the previous design. And from the design illustrations is seen that the new design is not just a scaled version of the $\epsilon_2 = 13$ design. This can be seen by comparing the connecting cylinders, which for the $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13.6$ optimized design have varying radius apposed to the design with $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13$. This result is in good agreement with the results from the preliminary optimization tests, in which it was seen that a larger dielectric contrast yields quantitatively different designs with larger band gaps.

(a) Isosurface plot of one unit cell of the optimized design. (b) Isosurface plot of a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ patch of unit cells of the optimized design.

Figure 5.11: Optimized design with a band gap of 17.7% between the fifth and sixth bands. The dielectric contrast is $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13.6$.

Figure 5.12: Banddiagram and element plot for the optimized design with a dielectric contrast of $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13.6$. The design has a complete band gap of 17.7 % between the fifth and sixth bands.

5.5 Summary of sc Optimization

It has been established that the implemented optimization problem is capable of producing 3D photonic band gap crystals in the sc lattice.

For the gap between the second and third bands an optimized design with a complete band gap of 8.5% was achieved. This corresponds to a 21 % increase in gap size compared to the best design presented in the literature. Similarly a 22% improvement in gap size compared to the literature was found for the optimized design with a 16.6% gap between the fifth and sixth bands. Both optimized designs was found to be more complex than designs reported in the literature and therefore more difficult to fabricate. However, both designs consists of connected regions of ϵ_2 , i.e. there is no ϵ_2 -material suspended in free air.

Furthermore the design problem of opening the 2-3 gap was tested using different initial guesses, which all converged to the same optimized design.

The optimized design with the 5-6 gap was recognized as a modification of the atomic inspired sc photonic crystal [Chern et al., 2007], i.e. instead of solid spheres at the lattice points the optimized design had hollow spheres at these points. The overlapping air sphere sc photonic crystal was then analyzed to test the scalability of Maxwell's EVP. This analysis showed that not only did the frequency shift according the theoretical prediction, but also the placement of the gap was shifted. Thus by scaling the original design by a factor $\frac{1}{2}$ the frequencies shifted by a factor 2, and the location of the band gap was shifted by a factor 8 corresponding to the number of unit cell within the unit cube, i.e. the 5-6 gap became a 40-41 gap.

Optimized Designs for the Diamond Lattice

This chapter concerns the optimization of 3D photonic crystals belonging to the diamond lattice. The diamond lattice is chosen since the 3D photonic crystals exhibiting the largest reported band gaps belong to this space lattice. As for the sc lattice the chapter starts with the introduction of the general framework for the optimization process, which is then followed by presenting the optimized designs.

As illustrated in Figure 1.2 in the introduction to the thesis, it is apparent that the fcc and diamond lattice are closely related. In fact the diamond type photonic crystals can be modelled using the Brillouin zone of the fcc lattice [Maldovan and Thomas, 2004, Joannopoulos et al., 1995]. This is because the diamond system can be obtained by adding four lattice points to the fcc lattice as seen in Figure 1.2. Note that the the fcc primitive cell is not a primitive cell for the diamond lattice.

As for the sc optimization problems its imperative that the diamond optimized

(a) Primitive cell of the fcc lattice in a unit cube.

(b) The active design variables consists of half the primitive cell along with the boundaries.

Figure 6.1: Illustration of the fcc primitive cell (left) and the active design variables in unit cube (right). For a mesh of $10 \times 10 \times 10$ elements there is a total of 200 active design variables.

designs follow the symmetries of the diamond lattice, such that the irreducible Brillouin zone can be used for predicting the optical behaviour of the design. In Figure 6.1 the primitive cell of the fcc lattice is shown next to a plot which illustrates the active design variables within the unit cube with respect to the diamond lattice.

It is found that there are 200 active design variables within the unit cube, which is considerably more than was the case for the sc lattice. Thus it is expected that the optimizer has greater freedom when optimizing the diamond system compared to the sc system. It is also seen from Figure 6.1 that only one mirror symmetry plane is present in the diamond lattice. And by geometric considerations it is found that the unit cube contains a total of four fcc primitive cells. Thus the symmetry operator for the diamond system consists of one mirror operation and a total of 12 translations of the centered primitive cell.

The fact that the unit cube contains four rhombohedral primitive cells, means that it is expected that the location of the band gaps will be shifted by a factor four compared to the results in the literature, c.f. Section 5.4. Though this issue is recognized to pose a problem with respect to CPU time, it has not been remedied in the work presented in this thesis.

To make the optimized designs comparable to results from the literature, the dielectric contrast is set to $\frac{\epsilon_2}{\epsilon_1} = 13$, and $\mu = 1$.

As was the case for the sc optimized designs, all optimized 3D designs of this Chapter can be found as Matlab Figure files on the CD accompanying this thesis, c.f. Appendix G.

6.1 Results from the Literature

As stated in the introduction to this Chapter, the 3D photonic crystals with the largest reported band gaps all belong to the diamond lattice, and all display the gap between bands two and three, when analyzed on the primitive cell.

Therefore it is no surprise that the literature is rich on different diamond like designs and it is far beyond the scope of this thesis to present them all. Instead the focus will be on the known designs with the largest band gaps, since it is hoped that the topology optimization programme developed in this thesis can produce designs with even larger gaps. For an overview of the top twenty diamond type crystals reported up to the year 2004 the reader is referred to [Maldovan and Thomas, 2004], while the best design reported yet can be found in [Chern et al., 2007] where a complete gap of 31.4% was shown to exist. This design, named the sp^3 diamond configuration, consists of dielectric spheres at lattice points connected by dielectric spheroids and can be seen illustrated in Figure 6.2a. Another interesting design is the so-called dielectric rod diamond configuration. This structure is seen in Figure 6.2b and has a band gap of 30%. This structure has attracted a considerable amount of attention since it is much simpler to manufacture than the sp^3 diamond configuration with techniques known today. However it must be emphasized that a photonic crystal with a 3D band gap within the visible spectrum has not been produced yet [Busch et al., 2007]

Figure 6.2: The two 3D photonic crystals with the largest reported band gaps.

6.1.1 Initial Designs for the Optimization Process

For the optimization results to be presented in the upcoming Sections three initial designs are considered. These have been chosen based on their differences such that the chance of ending up in the same local minimum is reduced.

The classic diamond type photonic crystal with a large band gap consists of a diamond lattice with overlapping air spheres of radius $0.325a$ situated at each of the lattice points. This design was originally presented by [Ho et al., 1990] and displays a gap of 29%. The design can be seen illustrated in Figure 6.3.

The second initial design is an inversion of the air sphere design presented above, i.e. instead of air spheres in a dielectric media, this design consists of dielectric spheres of radius $0.23a$ in a air. This design yields a complete band gap of 19% [Joannopoulos et al., 1995] and is shown in Figure 6.4.

The final initial design to be used for the diamond optimization is based on the fcc lattice, and consists of overlapping dielectric spheres with radius $0.4a$ situated at the fcc lattice points. This design does possess a complete band gap, though the two bands of interest does not intersect. The design and the corresponding band diagram are shown in Figure 6.5.

From the band structure of Figure 6.5b it is seen that the prediction of the shift in bands due to four primitive cells in the unit cube is correct, i.e. the gap of interest lies between the eighth and ninth bands which is four times higher than reported in the litterateur e.g. [Maldovan and Thomas, 2004].

Figure 6.3: The diamond photonic crystal consisting of overlapping air spheres of radius $0.325a$ at each lattice point. The gap between the second and third bands is found to be 29% c.f. [Ho et al., 1990].

Figure 6.4: The diamond photonic crystal consisting of overlapping dielectric spheres of radius $0.325a$ at each lattice point. The gap between the second and third bands is found to be 19% c.f. [Joannopoulos et al., 1995].

Figure 6.5: Initial guess based on dielectric spheres of radius $0.4a$ at the fcc lattice points in the unit cube. Note that this design does not have a complete band gap.

6.2 Optimization of Diamond Photonic Crystals

The goal of this Section is to maximize the gap between the eighth and ninth bands in the irreducible fcc Brillouin zone while allowing the design to attain symmetries of the diamond lattice. The wave vector is discretized by 19 uniformly spaced points and each EVP is solved for the first 14 eigenpairs if else not stated. The optimization will be based on the three initial designs presented in the previous Section.

6.2.1 Optimized Design based on the fcc Crystal

The first diamond lattice optimization problem to be presented in this thesis, is computed based on the initial guess consisting of the fcc-dielectric sphere design from Figure 6.5. From the band diagram of the initial guess, Figure 6.5b, it is observed that the two bands of interest do not intersect. However, it was found that using this starting guess together with the complete path around the irreducible Brillouin zone lead to very poor convergence, i.e. after 70 iterations on a $16 \times 16 \times 16$ mesh a band gap had not yet opened. This problem could most likely be remedied in several ways. One could play with the size of the active set, i.e. M , or one could compute a finer band structure in order to verify that the two bands of interest do not intersect, c.f. Figure 6.5b. In this work a third choice was made. The slow convergence was cured by applying the zipper method for both the $W - K$ and the $X - U$ interval. This resulted in the two designs of Figure 6.6. The corresponding optimization details are listed in Table 6.1.

The two designs shown in Figure 6.6 are seen to look quite similar though the zipper method was applied on different parts of irreducible Brillouin zone. However by comparing the objective values it is seen that their optical characteristics are different, i.e. the design in Figure 6.6a has a 1.1% larger gap than the design in Figure 6.6b. The two designs also have different filling ratios, i.e. $\beta = 0.23$ and $\beta = 0.22$ for the designs in Figures 6.6b and 6.6a respectively. Also note that the design in Figure 6.6b had not fully converged, i.e. the job was terminated at iteration 100 with a design change of 0.017. Since the design in Figure 6.6a is seen to have the largest band gap, it is decided to continue optimizing this design by

	Initial design	Procedure	Mesh	M	$\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0}$	Iter.	$\mathbf{k}$
Step 0 _a	Figure 6.5	Zip: $W - K$	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	10	0.289	92	Uni.
Step 0 _b	Figure 6.5	Zip: $X - U$	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	10	0.278	100 (max!)	Uni.
Step 1	From step 0 _a	Normal	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	20	0.304	47	Non-uni.

Table 6.1: Optimization details for the designs shown in Figure 6.6a (step 0_a) and Figure 6.6b (step 0_b). The computation time was approximately 15 hours for each of the two step. Note that the optimization process for step 0_b was stopped prematurely with a design change of 0.017. The last column to the right describes the discretization of $\mathbf{k}$ where non-uniform refers to refinement in the $L - \Gamma - X$ interval.

(a) Optimized design corresponding to the optimization settings of step 0_a in Table 6.1. The design shows a complete gap of 28.9%.

(b) Optimized design corresponding to the optimization settings of step 0_b in Table 6.1. The design shows a complete gap of 27.8%.

Figure 6.6: Isosurface plots of the optimized designs presented in Table 6.1 step 0.

(a) Band diagram of the design in Figure 6.6a based on 67 uniformly spaced points around the Brillouin zone. The gap was found to be 28.9% based on the band diagram.

(b) DOS of the design from Figure 6.6a consisting of 4000 points evenly distributed in the Brillouin zone. This analysis showed the presence of a 28.7% gap.

Figure 6.7: Band diagram and DOS for the optimized design in Figure 6.6a and step 0_a of Table 6.1. Note that the band gap predicted by the DOS is 0.2% smaller than the prediction of the band diagram.

including the whole path around the Brillouin zone.

However, before continuing this work it seems relevant to verify that the irreducible Brillouin zone of the fcc lattice is adequate in describing the optical characteristics of the optimized design. Therefore a map of the DOS is made for the design in Figure 6.6a. This together with the band diagram can be seen in Figure 6.7.

By comparing the DOS to the band diagram, both shown in Figure 6.7, it is

seen that there is a small discrepancy between the two band gap sizes, i.e. the DOS predicts a 0.2% smaller gap than the gap predicted by the band diagram. A small analysis of this issue showed that the reason for the discrepancies lies in the discretization of the of the $L-\Gamma-X$ part of the irreducible Brillouin zone. Thus, by refining the discretization of the wave vector between $L-\Gamma-X$ it was found that the irreducible Brillouin zone is adequate in predicting the optical performance of the design in Figure 6.6a. Consequently, this analysis have shown that the critical points of the irreducible Brillouin zone do not coincide with the high symmetry points, as was the case for the sc lattice.

This specific issue is not directly touched upon in the literature, though it seems to be common knowledge since many publications use a finer discretization of the wave vector between the high symmetry points $L-\Gamma-X$ than elsewhere, e.g. [Chern et al., 2007].

The optimization process is then resumed using the design in Figure 6.6a as initial guess. The wave vector now includes all high symmetry points and is discretized by 37 non-uniformly spaced points, such that the spectrum $L-\Gamma-X$ is refined. The resulting optimized design is shown in Figures 6.8a, 6.8b and 6.9b together with the band structure seen in Figure 6.9a. The optimized design has a band gap of 30.4% as seen in Table 6.1, step 1. The corresponding filling ratio is $\beta = 0.21$, and it is seen that the ϵ_2 regions are connected.

The design is, as was the case for step 0_a and 0_b of Table 6.1, quite complex and therefore difficult to visualize clearly. Thus to cast light on some general characteristic the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ patch of isosurfaces in Figure 6.9b is rotated such that a hexagonal pattern emerges. Similarly, the hexagonal shape can be obtained by rotating the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ patch 90 degrees to either side. This indicates a strong

Figure 6.8: Plots of the optimized design after step 1 in Table 6.1 with a band gap of 30.4%.

(a) Band diagram corresponding to the design in Figure 6.8 which shows the presence of a 30.4% gap.

(b) Isosurface plot of a patch of $2 \times 2 \times 2$ unit cells of the design in Figure 6.8 rotated such that a hexagonal type structure is seen.

Figure 6.9: Band diagram based on a 97 point discretization of the wave vector and a patch of eight unit cells for the optimized design presented in Table 6.1, step 1.

similarity to the dielectric rod design from Figure 6.2b, though the mesh used for the modelling is too coarse to reveal any of the fine details about the connecting rods and their geometry. It is however verified that the rods are solid, i.e. no hidden cavities are present.

It is also noted from the band structure in Figure 6.9a that it is still the $L - \Gamma - X$ part of the wave spectrum that limits the size of the band gap.

Due to time issues the design process was not continued on a finer mesh. Nor was the DOS for the final the design computed. And due to the same reason, the design from Table 6.1, step 0_b was not investigated further.

6.2.2 Optimized Design based on Dielectric Spheres

The optimization performed in this Section is based on the diamond like photonic crystal with dielectric spheres at the lattice points, c.f. Figure 6.4. The wave vector is discretized by 23 points such that 17 points lies between the high symmetry points $L - \Gamma - X$.

The details of the optimization process is presented in Table 6.2 and the optimized design and corresponding band structure are shown in Figures 6.10 and 6.11 respectively. Due to time constraints on this thesis the optimization process in step 2 of Table 6.2 had not fully converged in time of writing, i.e. the design change was 0.123 at iteration 41. However, from the band diagram it is found that the band gap already has a relative size of 31.8% and that the critical points does not coincide with high symmetry points. The filling ratio of the optimized design is $\beta = 0.20$.

Though the optimization process had not fully converged, it is still possible to state some quantitative observations regarding the optimized design and its band gap. From Table 6.2 is observed that the objective function has attained a value which is 0.4% larger than that of the sp^3 diamond design. By inspection of the optimized design, Figure 6.10, it is moreover seen that the optimized design looks quantitatively similar to the sp^3 and dielectric rod crystal as seen in Figures 6.2.

	Initial design	Procedure	Mesh	M	$\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0}$	Iter.
Step 1	Figure 6.4	Normal	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	20	0.315	97
Step 2	Step 1	Normal	$24 \times 24 \times 24$	20	0.318	41 (!)

Table 6.2: Optimization details for the design shown in Figure 6.10. The computation time was approximately 64 hours. The exclamation mark at the iteration counter for step 2 indicates that the optimization process was terminated before convergence due to time issues, i.e. the design change at iteration 41 was 0.123.

Figure 6.10: Unit cell of the optimized design after step 2 in Table 6.2.

Figure 6.11: Band diagram and a patch of eight unit cells for the optimized design presented in Table 6.2.

That is, generally speaking all three designs consists of dielectric rods connecting the lattice points of the diamond crystal.

However differences are easy to spot. For examples it is difficult to see the presence of dielectric spheres in the optimized design, which is opposite to the sp^3 crystal. So though the optimized design have certain overall similarities with the sp^3 and dielectric rod photonic crystals, the differences are noticeable.

It should also be noted that it is possible to rotate the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ patch of unit cells such that hexagonal holes appear. This is similar to the equivalent plot of the optimized design presented in Section 6.2.1 Figure 6.9b. There is moreover a high level of similarity in the layout of the band diagrams corresponding to the two optimized designs, c.f. Figure 6.11a and 6.9a. However, the similarity is not easily seen when comparing the unit cells of Figure 6.10 and 6.8. Therefore one may speculate that the two designs are rotated versions of the same general design and that the optimizer is in fact approaching the same local minimum in both cases. It must however be heavily emphasized that a conclusion is not possible due to the lack of thoroughness in both optimization process's, i.e. the former is performed on a extremely coarse mesh and the latter has not fully converged.

6.2.3 Optimized Design based on Air spheres

The last optimization problem to be investigated in this thesis deals with the optimization of the air sphere diamond crystal as seen in Figure 6.3. As for the previous optimization example the wave vector is discretized by 23 points such that 17 points lies between the high symmetry points $L - \Gamma - X$.

The result of the optimization process is summarized in Table 6.3 and the optimized design is shown in Figure 6.12. The band structure is plotted in Figure 6.13 and shows that the optimized design has a complete band gap of 32.2%, which is almost 1% larger than the gap reported for the sp^3 configuration in [Chern et al., 2007]. The filling ratio is $\beta = 0.18$, which is noted to be the lowest filling ratio for the diamond optimized designs.

The optimization process shown in Table 6.3 shows that the continuation method has been used to transfer the design from a $16 \times 16 \times 16$ mesh to a $24 \times 24 \times 24$ mesh and that the total computation time was approximately four days.

The optimized design shown in Figure 6.12 is seen to be very similar to the dielectric rod crystal in Figure 6.2b. From the isosurface plot it is especially clear that the rods have varying radius which places the optimized design as a hybrid between the dielectric rod and sp^3 photonic crystals. Thus the optimized design does not present a new topology for a 3D photonic crystal though the current

	Initial design	Procedure	Mesh	M	$\frac{\Delta\omega}{\omega_0}$	Iter.
Step 1	Figure 6.3	Normal	$16 \times 16 \times 16$	20	0.314	81
Step 2	Step 1	Normal	$24 \times 24 \times 24$	20	0.322	85

Table 6.3: Optimization details for the design shown in Figure 6.12. The total computation time was approximately 100 hours.

Figure 6.12: Isosurface and element plot of the optimized design with a complete gap of 32.2%, c.f. the optimization history in Table 6.3

Figure 6.13: Band diagram and patch of eight unit cells for the optimized design presented in Table 6.3.

record for the largest band gap has been increased by 0.8%.

Comparing the band diagram and the $2 \times 2 \times 2$ patch of unit cells with the optimized designs presented in the previous two sections, again shows a noticeable similarity. That is, the critical points in the irreducible Brillouin zone are the same and again the hexagonal shape is visible in the optimized design.

6.3 Summary of Diamond Optimization

The results presented in this Chapter have verified that the optimization program is capable of optimizing photonic crystals of the diamond lattice.

Three design problems based on different initial guesses was investigated, all with the objective of opening a band gap between the eighth and ninth bands.

The optimized results was found to be of complex geometry and therefore difficult to visualize for the reader. However certain similarities was seen. All three optimized designs has the same general layout of dielectric rods connecting the lattice points in the diamond lattice. Moreover their band structures had several similarities, e.g. the critical points of all three designs lies between the $L - \Gamma - X$ spectrum of the irreducible Brillouin zone. The last optimization problem was the only one to be analyzed on $24 \times 24 \times 24$ meshes and the result was a design with a complete band gap of 32.2%. This is a 2.6% improvement in the size of the band gap compared to the largest reported gap in the literature [Chern et al., 2007].

Unfortunately time did not allow the first two design problems to be fully analysed on a $24 \times 24 \times 24$ FE mesh, and therefore it is not possible to conclude that they all converge to the same optimized design.

The main computational burden of diamond optimization compared to sc optimization is that each unit cube contains four primitive cells. This means that the

iterative EVP solver needs to work on a larger subspace which results in slower convergence. It would therefore be advantageous to model the diamond lattice on a fcc primitive cell.

Conclusion and Future Work

In the following, the main findings of this thesis are summarized and suggestions for future work are discussed. Finally, the general conclusion of the thesis is presented.

7.1 Thesis Summary

The physical law governing the macroscopic properties of an infinitely periodic 3D photonic band gap crystal is presented in the form of Maxwell's EVP on a unit cell. The Bloch wave representation is included through periodic boundary conditions to enable the eigenmodes to attain periodicity different to that of the unit cell. This inclusion lead to the important concept of the band diagram and thereby the definition of a photonic band gap, i.e. a frequency interval for which no propagating modes exists. It also showed that the modeling of photonic crystals requires the solution of several EVPs, i.e. one for each wave vector within the irreducible Brillouin zone. For the numerical solution of Maxwell's EVP, a stabilized finite element formulation is derived using edge elements. A topology optimization problem for maximizing the band gap of photonic crystals is formulated using an active set strategy. To ensure it is possible to open band gaps that are not present in the initial design, the so-called zipper method is presented and discussed. The optimization problem is solved for local optimality using the gradient based non-linear optimization algorithm MMA. The sensitivity analysis is derived for both single eigenvalues, as well as for multiple eigenvalues, and a sensitivity update according to the symmetries of the crystal lattice is introduced.

The optimization problem is successfully implemented in Matlab using the finite element package COMSOL Multiphysics for solving the EVPs and computing the sensitivities. This choice is made due to the complexity and difficulty associated with implementing an efficient EVP solver. The Matlab/COMSOL implementation of the topology optimization problem is verified by means of a convergence analysis for the EVP and finite difference validation of the sensitivities. Since 3D simulations are computationally expensive, implementation issues are important. The main computational burden is found to be the solution of the EVPs. As a consequence of the embarrassingly parallel nature of the Bloch form of Maxwell's

EVP, the solution process is parallelized. This lead to a speedup of 5.75 for 7 CPUs for a problem with 22 entries in the wave vector. It was found that in order to obtain good parallel scalability the number of wave vector entries must exceed the number of CPUs. However, since the EVP solver is based on direct solution of the linear system of equations, it was found that the problem size was limited to approximately 14000 elements. With respect to the design resolution, this is considered as coarse and therefore fully iterative schemes such as the multigrid method is found to be promising, though not incorporated in the implementation.

Preliminary optimization test are carried out to validate the implemented optimization problem. The 1D problem of Bragg gratings is considered due to the availability of analytical results. These tests showed that the optimization formulation works and produce optimized designs in good agreement with the analytical predictions. An investigation of the influence of different sizes of active set shows that a too small set yields oscillatory convergence and that a too large set yields slow convergence. The smoothness of the considered optimization problem is examined, and reveals that though it is not strictly smooth, it converges to the analytical result better than the truly smooth bound formulation.

The optimization program is applied to the synthesis of sc 3D photonic crystals with a dielectric contrast of 13. For the problem of maximizing the gap between bands 2-3, it is found that the same optimized design is obtained based on three significantly different initial guesses. The optimized design has a band gap of 8.5% which is 21% larger compared to the largest gap reported in the literature. Optimizing the gap between bands five and six leads to a design with a band gap of 16.6%. This is a 22% improvement compared to the literature. It is observed that both optimized designs are similar to the ones presented in the literature, though the optimized design contains finer geometries and thus are more difficult to fabricate. It is furthermore observed that finer meshing leads to larger band gaps, which illustrates the need for a better EVP solver. Finally a scaling study reveals that when modelling eight unit cells with the unit cube, leads to a shift in the location of the band gap by a factor eight, i.e. gap 5-6 becomes gap 40-41.

The final design problem concerns the optimization of photonic crystals in the diamond lattice, again with a dielectric contrast of 13. In this setting the unit cube contains four primitive cells, and as expected it is found that the band gap is located between gap 8-9, apposed to 2-3 as seen in the literature. The optimization is based on three different initial guesses. Due to time issues only one of the optimization problems has fully converged, which means that though the three designs are very similar it is not possible to draw conclusions as to whether or not they converge to the same optimized design. The converged design has a band gap of 32.2% which is a 2.6% improvement compared to the best design found in the literature. As for the sc optimized designs, the similarities between diamond optimized design and designs from the literature is striking.

7.2 Future Work

The obvious extension of this work is to complete the study of the diamond 3D photonic crystal, i.e. solve the remaining two example problems on a $24 \times 24 \times 24$ mesh such that the designs and their objective values can be compared to the fully converged design. Another natural extension is to optimize crystals belonging to e.g. the body-centered cubic lattice, the hexagonal lattice, etc. in hope of determining completely new 3D photonic crystals with large band gaps. Likewise there could be other locations of band gaps, which have not yet been seen, since they have not been attempted opened. Thus a systematic study of all possible gap locations for a given crystal lattice would be of significant relevance.

Since it is extremely difficult to visualize the 3D geometries, it would be very helpful to fabricate the optimized designs for hands on inspection, e.g. a unit cell of $10 \times 10 \times 10$ cm. This would also help the comparison of the three different optimized diamond crystals. And in direct continuation of this, it could be exciting to fabricate the designs in e.g. the micro-wave regime and experimentally verify the optimized designs optical properties. Also with respect to manufactureability, it could be interesting to apply a minimum lengthscale filter to ensure geometric tolerances was above a certain threshold.

Regarding the modelling aspect of this work, numerous extension can be thought of, e.g. the implementation of a fully iterative and efficient eigenvalue solver, parallelization of the sensitivity analysis and a generalized method of implementing arbitrary crystal lattice symmetries. It could also be interesting to model a large patch of unit cells and compute the transmission and reflection of different incident waves with frequencies within the band gap. This is especially interesting since it would violate the Bloch theorem which assumes infinite periodicity.

Finally it could also be quite interesting to allow metallic inclusions in the design and thereby enable the optimization of the so-called metamaterials, i.e. materials with negative effective ϵ and/or μ . These materials are however prone to several modelling difficulties, and therefore a more realistic extension, though challenging, could be to include material non-linearities such that e.g. gap solitons can be modelled and optimized [Busch et al., 2007].

7.3 Perspectives

Though the work presented in this thesis have shown that the method of topology optimization is a usefull tool in the design of 3D photonic band gap crystals, it is not likely to become an industrial design aid within the near future. This is a consequence of the lack in fabrication methods for fully 3D photonic crystals.

7.4 Conclusion

The main objective of this thesis is to apply the method of topology optimization to the synthesis of 3D photonic crystals. This objective has been accomplished

and it has been demonstrated that the method of topology optimization can be applied as an efficient numerical tool for the design of sc and diamond 3D photonic band gap crystals. It has also been found that the band gaps of the optimized designs outperforms the best designs from the literature with an improvement of approximately 2% and 20% for the diamond and sc photonic crystals respectively. There is however still issues to be dealt with, especially concerning the EVP solver, but also with respect to manufactureability.

Maxwell's Equations on Differential Form

A.1 Timevarying Form and Constitutive Relations

Maxwell's equations in a linear, isotropic material states the relation between the timevarying electric field, $\mathbf{E} = \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and timevarying magnetic field, $\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}(\mathbf{x}, t)$, and their sources, charges and current densities. On differential form the equations can be stated as follows where all quantities are assumed to be both functions of time and space [Balanis, 1989], see Table A.1 for details on symbols and their names.

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \quad \text{Faraday's law} \quad (\text{A.1.1})$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{J}^{imp} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{D}}{\partial t} \quad \text{Ampère's law} \quad (\text{A.1.2})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{D} = \rho_e \quad \text{Gauss' law} \quad (\text{A.1.3})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0 \quad \text{Gauss' law} \quad (\text{A.1.4})$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\mathbf{J} + \mathbf{J}^{imp}) = -\frac{\partial \rho_e}{\partial t} \quad \text{Continuity} \quad (\text{A.1.5})$$

where the last equation is known as the *continuity equation* and states the relation between current density and charge density. Note that this extra equation can be derived from Faraday's law, and therefore is dependent.

Similar to solid mechanics, constitutive relations are needed to describe the atomic behaviour on a macroscopic level, i.e. how charged particles interacts with the electromagnetic fields and produce currents and modifies the electromagnetic wave propagation. For Maxwell's equations three such constitutive relations are constructed [Balanis, 1989]. The electric and magnetic fields are related to the electric and magnetic fluxes $\mathbf{D}$ and $\mathbf{B}$ through the constitutive laws

$$\mathbf{B} = \mu_0(\mathbf{H} + \mathbf{P}_m) = \mu_0\mu_r\mathbf{H} = \mu\mathbf{H} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{P}_m = \chi_m\mathbf{H} \quad (\text{A.1.6})$$

$$\mathbf{D} = \epsilon_0\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{P}_e = \epsilon_0\epsilon_r\mathbf{E} = \epsilon\mathbf{E} \quad \text{and} \quad \mathbf{P}_e = \epsilon_0\chi_e\mathbf{E} \quad (\text{A.1.7})$$

where the non-dimensional quantities $\mu_r = 1 + \chi_m$ and $\epsilon_r = 1 + \chi_e$ are the relative permeability and permittivity respectively and χ_m and χ_e are the magnetic and

electric susceptibility. The electric current density is related to the electric field by

$$\mathbf{J} = \sigma \mathbf{E} \quad (\text{A.1.8})$$

Finally one should note that only three of the five equations, (A.1.1) to (A.1.5), are independent, and therefore choices must be made when searching for solutions. For example the first two equations accompanied by either of Gauss' laws form an independent system or the continuity equation, Ampères law and a one of the two gauge condition, i.e. eq. (A.1.3) or (A.1.4), [Balanis, 1989].

Quantity	Name	Quantity	Name
$\mathbf{E}$	Electric field	ρ_e	electric charge density
$\mathbf{H}$	Magnetic field	ϵ_0	permittivity of free space
$\mathbf{D}$	Electric flux density	μ_0	permeability of free space
$\mathbf{B}$	Magnetic flux density	ϵ	effective permittivity
$\mathbf{P}_e$	Electric polarization vector	μ	effective permeability
$\mathbf{P}_m$	Magnetic polarization vector	σ	conductivity
$\mathbf{J}$	Electric current density	$\mathbf{J}^{imp}$	Prescribed impressed current

Table A.1: Quantities and their names in Maxwell's equations.

A.2 Timeharmonic Form

The previous section described how general time-varying electromagnetic fields interacts. However in many practical applications the time variations are of sinusoidal form, e.g. propagation of light, and the equations can be recast on timeharmonic form in which time is no longer present. Thus assuming that the time varying fields are harmonic, one may write them as $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}, t) = \Re [\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x})e^{j\omega t}]$, etc., where ω is the frequency, t is time and $\Re$ denotes the real part. Inserting this into eqs. (A.1.1) to (A.1.5), and utilizing the constitutive laws, Maxwell's equations on timeharmonic form becomes

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = -j\omega\mu\mathbf{H} \quad \text{Faraday's law} \quad (\text{A.2.1})$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} = j\omega\epsilon\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{J}^{imp} \quad \text{Ampère's law} \quad (\text{A.2.2})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \epsilon\mathbf{E} = \rho_e \quad \text{Gauss' law} \quad (\text{A.2.3})$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mu\mathbf{H} = 0 \quad \text{Gauss' law} \quad (\text{A.2.4})$$

$$\nabla \cdot (\sigma\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J}^{imp}) = -j\omega\rho \quad \text{Continuity} \quad (\text{A.2.5})$$

Note that is now assumed that ϵ , μ , ρ and σ do not depend on time nor frequency [Balanis, 1989].

The two first order curl equations can be cast as one second order PDE in only $\mathbf{E}$ or $\mathbf{H}$ - the choice depends mainly on BCs and type of loading. Below it is shown how an electrical formulation is obtained.

$$\begin{aligned}
\mathbf{H} &= \frac{-1}{j\omega\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \quad , \text{ insert into (A.2.2)} \quad \Rightarrow \\
\nabla \times \frac{-1}{j\omega\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) &= j\omega\epsilon\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{J}^{imp} \quad \Rightarrow \\
\nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) - \omega^2\epsilon\mathbf{E} &= -j\omega\sigma\mathbf{E} - j\omega\mathbf{J}^{imp} \quad (\text{A.2.6})
\end{aligned}$$

Finally in order to make the system complete, the gauge condition for the electric flux is added to the PDE system, and the resulting problem becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
\nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) + (j\omega\sigma - \omega^2\epsilon)\mathbf{E} &= -j\omega\mathbf{J}^{imp} \\
\nabla \cdot \epsilon\mathbf{E} &= 0
\end{aligned}$$

This is the system of equations which together with appropriate boundary conditions will be attacked in this report.

Note that the curl-curl equation could be rewritten such that the Laplace operator appears and the divergence condition is naturally included. This however is not done, since the tangential continuity at material interfaces then becomes difficult to impose.

Weak form derivation

The weak form of Maxwell's EVP, eqs. (2.1.4), can be obtained using several approaches. In this derivation the standard Galerkin method is applied. All Galerkin methods consists of multiplying the PDE with a suitable test function and integrating over the domain, such that partial integration can be used to reduce the order of the PDE, and thereby expanding the space in which solutions can exist. The standard Galerkin method is then to choose the test functions, to be the same as the expansion functions for the solution itself. The notation and mathematical tools needed for this are adopted from [Zaglmayr, 2006], [Jin, 2002] and [Demkowicz, 2003]. For simplicity the subscript $(\cdot)_{nk}$ is suppressed in the derivation.

Let $\mathbf{F}$ be a vector valued test function that is zero on the boundary Γ . Then application of the Galerkin method on the curl-curl equation yields

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{F}^H \nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \Rightarrow \\ \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{F})^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \cdot \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega \\ + \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{F}^H \left[\mathbf{n} \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \right] \, d\partial\Omega = 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.0.1})$$

where $(\cdot)^H$ means transposed complex conjugate. Now utilize that $\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{H} = -j\omega \mathbf{J}^{sur} = 0$ since no surface sources are present. Rewriting using Faraday's law to $\mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{H} = \mathbf{n} \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) = 0$ leads to

$$\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{F})^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \cdot \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \quad (\text{B.0.2})$$

The right space in which to look for solutions for electric field is the Sobolev space $H(\text{curl}, \Omega) = \{\mathbf{E} \in \mathbf{L}_2(\Omega) \mid \nabla \times \mathbf{E} \in \mathbf{L}_2(\Omega)\}$, where $\mathbf{L}_2(\Omega)$ is the vector space of square integrable functions in the Lebesgue sense [Hansen, 2006], i.e. for a scalar function $L_2(\Omega) = \{u \mid \int_{\Omega} u^2 \, d\Omega < \infty\}$ and thus $\mathbf{L}_2(\Omega) = [L_2(\Omega)]^3$. This choice

assures that the internal energy of the system is finite. This means that only the components

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} = \{E_{y,z} - E_{z,y}, E_{z,x} - E_{x,z}, E_{x,y} - E_{y,x}\} \quad (\text{B.0.3})$$

are required to be square integrable while the $E_{x,x}, E_{y,y}$, etc. are not.

Though the $H(\text{curl})$ -space is well suited for the approximate solution of Maxwell equations, it has a large null-space, which can be illustrated upon replacing $\mathbf{F}$ with the gradient of a scalar function ϕ in the Maxwell EVP.

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \nabla \phi)^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon (\nabla \phi)^H \cdot \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \\ \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon (\nabla \phi)^H \cdot \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \end{aligned}$$

where the identity $\nabla \times \nabla \phi = 0$ has been used. From this it can be seen that the eigenvalue $\omega^2 = 0$ corresponds to an infinite space of gradient functions. However, following the results of [Zaglmayr, 2006], it can be shown that for the discrete set of eigenvalues $\omega_i^2 \neq 0$, the corresponding eigenmode $\mathbf{E}_i$ satisfies the equation $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E}_i = 0$, and therefore a stable formulation can be obtained when including this as a constraint. Also note that this constraint is indeed the gauge condition from Maxwell's equations.

The divergence condition can be imposed e.g. by taking both PDE's in (2.1.4) into account and introducing a new variable ψ . The idea is then to add $\epsilon \nabla \psi$ to the curl-curl equation, and apply the Galerkin method to the entire system.

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) - \omega^2 \epsilon \mathbf{E} + \epsilon \nabla \psi = 0 \\ \nabla \cdot \epsilon \mathbf{E} = 0 \Rightarrow \\ \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{F}^H \nabla \times \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \nabla \psi \, d\Omega = 0 \\ \int_{\Omega} \phi \nabla \cdot \epsilon \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \Rightarrow \\ \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{F})^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \cdot \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{F}^H \nabla \psi \, d\Omega = 0 \\ \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \nabla \phi^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = 0 \end{aligned}$$

where ϕ is the test function for the divergence condition, which should be chosen from the Sobolev space $H_0^1(\Omega) = \{\phi \in L_2(\Omega) \mid \nabla \phi \in \mathbf{L}_2(\Omega)\} \mid \phi|_{\partial\Omega} = 0\}$. The partial integration has been performed using

$$\int_{\Omega} \phi \nabla \cdot \epsilon \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \nabla \phi^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega - \int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{n} \cdot (\phi \mathbf{E}) \, d\partial\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.4})$$

where the boundary term disappears due to the choice of test function space, i.e. $\int_{\partial\Omega} \mathbf{n} \cdot (\phi \mathbf{E}) \, d\partial\Omega = 0$.

The same result can be obtained using Lagrangian multipliers, which is easier, since no good idea is needed. Let Π be the functional given by the internal energy

$$\Pi = \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E})^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}) \, d\Omega - \omega^2 \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{E}^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.5})$$

Then by introducing ψ as a Lagrangian multiplier, the divergence condition is added to Π to form $\tilde{\Pi}$

$$\tilde{\Pi} = \Pi + \int_{\Omega} \psi \nabla \cdot \epsilon \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega = \Pi + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon (\nabla \psi)^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.6})$$

Requiring stationarity of $\tilde{\Pi}$, i.e. $\delta \tilde{\Pi} = 0$ where $\delta \tilde{\Pi} = \frac{\partial \tilde{\Pi}}{\partial v_i} \delta v_i$ with $v_1 = \mathbf{E}$ and $v_2 = \psi$ yields

$$\delta \tilde{\Pi} = \delta \Pi + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon [\nabla(\delta \psi)]^H \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega + \int_{\Omega} \epsilon (\nabla \psi)^H \delta \mathbf{E} \, d\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.7})$$

Where it has been used that the variation and partial differentiation can be interchanged. In this functional $\delta \mathbf{E}$ and $\delta \psi$ are seen to be analogues to test functions $\mathbf{F}$ and ϕ , and it is seen that the two approaches include the divergence condition in an identical manner.

The resulting weak form of Maxwell's EVP including the divergence condition can be written on variational form as find $\omega^2 \in R^+$, $\mathbf{E} \in H(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ and $\psi \in H^1(\Omega)$ such that

$$\begin{aligned} a(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{F}) + b(\phi, \mathbf{F}) &= \omega^2 c(\mathbf{E}, \mathbf{F}) \\ b(\mathbf{E}, \psi)^H &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.0.8})$$

$\forall \mathbf{F} \in H_0(\text{curl}, \Omega)$ and $\forall \phi \in H_0^1(\Omega)$. This type of formulation is recognized as a saddle point problem [Zaglmayr, 2006].

By replacing $\mathbf{E}$ and $\mathbf{F}$ with its discrete counterpart $\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{x}) \approx \sum_{e=1}^n \mathbf{N}^e(\mathbf{x}) \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^e$ where $\mathbf{N}$ is the shape function matrix, n is the number of finite elements and $\tilde{\mathbf{E}}$ is the expansion coefficients to be solved for. Thus the functions in $\mathbf{N}(\mathbf{x})$ should be chosen from the discrete version of $H(\text{curl}, \Omega)$. This class of functions are named after Nedeléc who was the first to apply them in FEM, but can also be found in the literature as edge- or vector-elements. A similar approximation is introduced for ϕ and ψ , only here standard nodal Lagrangian shape function are used [Cook et al., 2002]. Insertion into the weak form and equating to zero yields the algebraic EVP. For simplicity the tilde's are dropped from the notation.

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}^H & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \psi \end{Bmatrix} = \omega^2 \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \psi \end{Bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.0.9})$$

The computation of the respective matrices should be straightforward and can be found in Appendix F¹. Finally one should note that neither the weak form

¹for first order edge-elements for $\mathbf{E}$ and 1st order Lagrange elements for ψ

nor the algebraic problem includes Dirichlet conditions, which must be handled using separate methods, such as Lagrange multipliers, elimination or penalization [Cook et al., 2002].

A similar procedure can be performed on the boundary value problem, which leads to the algebraic problem of solving

$$\left(\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{K} & \mathbf{B} \\ \mathbf{B}^H & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} + (j\omega\sigma/\epsilon - \omega^2) \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{M} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix} \right) \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{E} \\ \psi \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} \mathbf{f} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (\text{B.0.10})$$

Note that the only difference between the BVP and EVP is the presence of a conductivity matrix and a load vector. The expression for the respective matrices and vectors in the FE form of Maxwell's equations are given below.

$$\mathbf{K} = \int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{N}_E)^H \frac{1}{\mu} (\nabla \times \mathbf{N}_E) \, d\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.11})$$

$$\mathbf{M} = \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{N}_E^H \mathbf{N}_E \, d\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.12})$$

$$\mathbf{f} = -j\omega \int_{\Omega} \mathbf{N}_E^H \mathbf{J}^{imp} \, d\Omega - j\omega \int_{\Gamma} \mathbf{n} \times \mathbf{J}^{sur} \, d\Gamma \quad (\text{B.0.13})$$

$$\mathbf{B} = \int_{\Omega} \epsilon \nabla \mathbf{N}_{\psi}^H \mathbf{N}_E \, d\Omega \quad (\text{B.0.14})$$

Optimization

This appendix is to be read in conjunction with, or after having read Chapter 2.4, since the nomenclature needed to appreciate the context is given in there aforementioned Chapter.

C.1 Bound Formulation

Bound reformulation of (P), see e.g. [Andréasson et al., 2005] for details.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{(\mathbf{E}, \omega), \gamma \in \mathbb{R}^{N+2}} \quad & \phi_0(\gamma) = 2 \frac{\gamma_2 - \gamma_1}{\gamma_2 + \gamma_1} \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & \left(\tilde{\mathbf{K}} - \omega_n^2(\mathbf{k}) \tilde{\mathbf{M}}(\gamma) \right) \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_{nk} = \mathbf{0}, \quad k \in K \\
 & \gamma_1 - \omega_{j+1}^k \leq 0, \quad k \in K \\
 & \omega_j^k - \gamma_2 \leq 0, \quad k \in K \\
 & 0 \leq \gamma_i \leq 1, \quad \text{for } j = 3, N+2
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{P}_0$$

This problem is smooth, hence differentiable and therefore solvable by standard non-linear gradient based optimizers. The two extra variables, γ_1 and γ_2 , are not included in the box constraints and can thus take on any real valued number. Note that the objective function in $(P)_0$ improves if both γ_1 and γ_2 are lowered by the same amount. This is also clearly the case in the original problem formulation.

C.2 Sensitivity Derivation

The sensitivities of ω_j with respect to a design variable γ_i can be derived directly from the EVP in eq. 2.1.4. The derivation assumes that the system matrices are Hermitian, that $\mathbf{M}$ is positive definite, and that the eigenpair $(\omega_j, \mathbf{E}_j)$ is unique, i.e. not a multiple eigenvalue. Written on matrix form the sensitivity becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 (\mathbf{K} - \omega_j^2 \mathbf{M}) \mathbf{E}_j = \mathbf{0} \quad & \Rightarrow \quad \frac{d}{d\gamma_i} [(\mathbf{K} - \omega_j^2 \mathbf{M}) \mathbf{E}_j] = 0 \quad \Rightarrow \\
 (\mathbf{K} - \omega_j^2 \mathbf{M}) \frac{d\mathbf{E}_j}{d\gamma_i} + \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_i} - \omega_j^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_i} - \frac{d\omega_j^2}{d\gamma_i} \mathbf{M} \right) \mathbf{E}_j = 0 \quad & \Rightarrow
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\underbrace{\mathbf{E}_j^H (\mathbf{K} - \omega_j^2 \mathbf{M})}_{=0} \frac{d\mathbf{E}_j}{d\gamma_i} + \mathbf{E}_j^H \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_i} - \omega_j^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_i} \right) \mathbf{E}_j - \frac{d\omega_j^2}{d\gamma_i} \mathbf{E}_j^H \mathbf{M} \mathbf{E}_j = 0 \Rightarrow$$

$$\frac{d\omega_j^2}{d\gamma_i} = \frac{\mathbf{E}_j^H \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_i} - \omega_j^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_i} \right) \mathbf{E}_j}{\mathbf{E}_j^H \mathbf{M} \mathbf{E}_j} \quad (\text{C.2.1})$$

Here it should be noted that no assumptions were made about the type of normalization of the eigenvector $\mathbf{E}_j$. However if $\mathbf{E}_j$ had been mass normalized the denominator would be 1, as in [Pedersen, 2006, Seyranian et al., 1994]. Finally using the chain-rule the sensitivity of ω_j can be given as

$$\frac{d\omega_j}{d\gamma_i} = \frac{\partial \omega_j}{\partial \omega_j^2} \frac{d\omega_j^2}{d\gamma_i} = \frac{1}{2\omega_j} \frac{\mathbf{E}_j^H \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_i} - \omega_j^2 \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_i} \right) \mathbf{E}_j}{\mathbf{E}_j^H \mathbf{M} \mathbf{E}_j} \quad (\text{C.2.2})$$

Similarly the sensitivity can be stated on integral form as

$$\frac{d\omega_j}{d\gamma_i} = \frac{1}{2\omega_j} \frac{\int_{\Omega} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}_j)^H \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial \gamma_i} (\nabla \times \mathbf{E}_j) d\Omega - \omega_j^2 \int_{\Omega} \frac{\partial \epsilon}{\partial \gamma_i} \mathbf{E}_j^H \mathbf{E}_j d\Omega}{\int_{\Omega} \epsilon \mathbf{E}_j^H \mathbf{E}_j d\Omega} \quad (\text{C.2.3})$$

Note that in photonic crystal optimization the permeability is independent of the design variables and therefore the expression can be simplified by letting $(\partial \frac{1}{\mu})/(\partial \gamma_i)$ be zero.

C.3 Sensitivities of Multiple Eigenvalues

Optimization problems involving frequencies is prone to the presence of multiple eigenfrequencies. For highly symmetric structures, e.g. photonic crystals, the problem is even more likely to occur. The problem is that if $\mathbf{E}_1$ and $\mathbf{E}_2$ are both eigenvectors with frequency ω , then any linear combination of the two will also be an eigenvector to ω . This means the expression derived in eq. (C.2.1) may fail, since this was based on the assumption of unique eigenvectors as well as frequencies.

Therefore a method is needed which can compute the sensitivities in the presence of multiple frequencies. Such a method is given in [Pedersen, 2006] and this Appendix is intended as a short presentation of the method.

The method is a perturbation method and basically works by formulating a subeigenvalue problem and then to extract the directional derivatives, i.e. sensitivities, based on these. Here the method is presented according to [Pedersen, 2006], since this form is easiest compared to the implementation in Appendix H.3.

Assume that an eigenvalue, $\lambda = \omega^2$, has a h -fold multiplicity and that the corresponding eigenvectors are $\mathbf{M}$ -orthonormalized, i.e.

$$\mathbf{E}_i^H \mathbf{M} \mathbf{E}_j = \delta_{ij} \quad \text{for } (i, j) = 1, \dots, h \quad (\text{C.3.1})$$

where δ_{ij} is Kroneckers delta. Then utilizing that any linear combination of the eigenvectors is also an eigenvector for λ we may write

$$\tilde{\mathbf{E}} = \sum_{i=1}^h \mathbf{E}_i c_i \quad (\text{C.3.2})$$

where c_i are constants. If we determine the constants such that $\sum_i^h c_i^2 = 1$ we directly get

$$\sum_i^h c_i^2 = 1 \Rightarrow \tilde{\mathbf{E}}^H \mathbf{M} \tilde{\mathbf{E}} = 1 \quad (\text{C.3.3})$$

i.e. that the linear combination is also mass normalized. Inserting this into eq. (C.2.1) yields

$$\frac{d\lambda}{d\gamma_e} = \sum_{i=1}^h \sum_{j=1}^h c_i c_j G_{ij} \quad (\text{C.3.4})$$

where the subscript $(\cdot)_e$ refers to the specific design variable and the Hermitian matrix $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{h \times h}$ is given by

$$G_{ij} = \mathbf{E}_i^H \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma_e} - \lambda \frac{\partial \mathbf{M}}{\partial \gamma_e} \right) \mathbf{E}_j \quad (\text{C.3.5})$$

The idea is then to determine the extremal values of this expression with the constraint that $\sum_i^h c_i^2 = 1$. For this purpose we form the Lagrangian [Andréasson et al., 2005] by adding a zero to eq. (C.3.4) which again leads to the introduction of a new variable ν , i.e.

$$L(c_i, \nu) = \sum_{i=1}^h \sum_{j=1}^h (c_i c_j G_{ij}) + \nu \left(1 - \sum_i^h c_i^2 \right) \quad (\text{C.3.6})$$

As for any smooth unconstrained optimization problem the extremal values can be found by requiring stationarity of the Lagrangian. This means that one have to differentiate $L(c_i, \nu)$ with respect all c_i and ν and set it equal to zero. Performing these manipulations leads to yet a new eigenvalue problem of the form

$$(\mathbf{G} - \nu \mathbf{I}) \mathbf{c} = 0 \quad (\text{C.3.7})$$

where ν is the eigenvalues to be solved for and $\mathbf{c}_i$ are the eigenvectors. Using the result from [Seyranian et al., 1994], i.e. the pertubation analysis, it is found that the sensitivities of λ with respect to γ_e is simply the eigenvalue ν , i.e.

$$\frac{d\lambda}{d\gamma_e} = \begin{cases} \nu_1 \\ \nu_2 \\ \dots \\ \nu_h \end{cases} \quad (\text{C.3.8})$$

Thus for each design variable one have to solve a $h \times h$ eigenvalue proble in order to obtain needed the sensitivities. Note that the eigenvectors $\mathbf{c}$ are of no importance for the context of this thesis.

C.3.1 A Note on High Symmetry Points

As stated in Appendix C.3 the multiple eigenvalues *might* give rise to problems with the sensitivity expression of eq. (C.2.1). Thus there are circumstances where multiple eigenvalues do not ruin the therein presented scheme. Following the results from [Kosakaa and Swan, 1999] this can be explained very simply using geometry. In Figure C.1 a square symmetric 2D lattice is shown with its corresponding Brillouin zone, i.e. the red triangle. In the Figures C.1a and C.1b two typical modeshapes originating at a high symmetry point is sketched illustratively. Note that the Brillouin zone coincides with the symmetry lines of the square lattice. As described in Section 2.4.4 eq. (2.4.10) the sensitivities must be updated according to the symmetry lines. Thus it is clearly seen that, though the modeshapes are different, the summation of the sensitivities will lead to the same result whether the modeshape in Figure C.1a or C.1b is used.

Though this can lead to correct sensitivities using eq. (C.2.1) in some cases, it must be emphasized that the method presented in Appendix C.3 is indeed needed, since not all multiple eigenvalues occurs at high symmetry points as seen in e.g. Chapter 6.

Figure C.1: Sketch of two modeshapes at a point of high symmetry. Note that one is a 90 degree rotation of the other, and that the red triangles illustrates the symmetry lines of the square lattice.

C.4 The Minimum Compliance Problem

The classic problem in topology optimization is that of linear elastic compliance minimization [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004], for which the optimization problem can be written as

$$\begin{aligned}
 \min_{\boldsymbol{\rho} \in \mathbb{R}^N} \quad & \mathbf{f}^T \mathbf{u} && \text{Compliance} \\
 \text{s.t.} \quad & \mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f} && \text{State equations} \\
 \text{(P)}_c \quad & \sum_e^N \rho_e V_e \leq V^* && \text{Volume constraint} \\
 & 0 \leq \rho_e \leq 1, \quad \text{for } e = 1, N && \text{Box constraint}
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{u}$ is a vector of displacements and $\mathbf{K} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}$ is the FE equation with $\mathbf{K}$ being the stiffness matrix and $\mathbf{f}$ being the load vector. The superscript T denotes the vector transpose. The second constraint limits the amount of material to V^* where V_e is the element volume, and is needed to avoid trivial designs i.e. a design domain full of material. The design variables, $\boldsymbol{\rho} \in \mathbb{R}^N$, can be regarded as densities, and are introduced to the problem through

$$\mathbf{K} = \sum_e^N \mathbf{K}_0^e \rho_e^p \tag{C.4.2}$$

where $p \approx 3$ is a penalization factor and $\mathbf{K}_0^e$ is a reference element stiffness matrix. This material interpolation scheme is known as Solid Isotropic Material with Penalization (SIMP).

The SIMP interpolation is applied to ensure black and white designs, i.e. either material or no material, apposed to intermediate unphysical materials as would be the case with a linear interpolation. The SIMP method works by making sure that intermediate densities yields a low stiffness. This is costly with respect to the volume constraint, and therefore the optimization will lead to 0 – 1 designs [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004].

The optimization problem is however prone to another troublesome problem. This is partly of physical and partly of numerical origin and results in mesh dependency and checkerboards respectively. The first issue stems from the fact that thin and closely packed membranes yields a less compliant structure than the same amount of solid material, e.g. human bone structure resembles this fact. The latter issue stems from numerics, i.e. low order FE approximations. However, both issues can be dealt with using the same techniques, which all consists of some sort of filtering of the sensitivities or the densities [Bendsøe and Sigmund, 2004]. The sensitivity filter is the computationally cheapest and the easiest to implement. It works by smearing out the sensitivities over a predefined tolerance radius, i.e. it puts a minimum lengthscale on the problem.

Though the minimum compliance problem seems simple at first, it's a perfect illustration of the necessity for a sound physical understanding when setting up an optimization problem.

Brillouin zone and the Reciprocal Lattice

The Appendix contains a brief note on high symmetry points in the Brillouin zone, as well as short illustration of the Fourier analysis from which the first Brillouin zone has its origin.

D.1 High Symmetry Points

This Appendix provides the high symmetry points of the irreducible Brillouin zone for the sc and fcc crystal lattice. The specifics are stated in Table D.1.

Γ	$(0, 0, 0)$	X_{fcc}	$(2\pi, 0, 0)/a$
X_{sc}	$(\pi, 0, 0)/a$	U_{fcc}	$(2\pi, \frac{1}{2}\pi, \frac{1}{2}\pi)/a$
M_{sc}	$(\pi, \pi, 0)/a$	W_{fcc}	$(2\pi, \pi, 0)/a$
R_{sc}	$(\pi, \pi, \pi)/a$	K_{fcc}	$(\frac{3}{2}\pi, \frac{3}{2}\pi, 0)/a$
		L_{fcc}	$(\pi, \pi, \pi)/a$

Table D.1: High symmetry points of the irreducible Brillouin zone for the sc and fcc lattice, where a is the lattice constant.

D.2 Fourier analysis and the Reciprocal lattice

Fourier analysis of the Y periodic dielectric function readily yields [Joannopoulos et al., 1995]

$$\epsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \epsilon(\mathbf{x} + Y) \Rightarrow$$

$$\epsilon(\mathbf{x}) = \int_X \epsilon(\mathbf{k}) e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} d\mathbf{k} = \int_X \epsilon(\mathbf{k}) e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot\mathbf{x}} e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot Y} d\mathbf{k} = \epsilon(\mathbf{x} + Y) \Rightarrow \quad (\text{D.2.1})$$

$$e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot Y} = 1 \quad (\text{D.2.2})$$

where $\epsilon(\mathbf{k})$ is the coefficient of the plane wave with wave vector $\mathbf{k}$. Thus by ignoring the trivial case when $\epsilon(\mathbf{k}) = 0$, we define any wave vector that satisfy the condition $e^{j\mathbf{k}\cdot Y} = 1$ (or $\mathbf{k}\cdot Y = 2n\pi$, $n = 1, 2, 3, \dots$) as the reciprocal lattice and denote it by $\mathbf{G}$.

The Electric Field Modes

The focus of this thesis is to design photonic crystals for which there exist frequency ranges with no propagation modes. Therefore much energy is spent on analyzing band diagrams and photonic crystal layout. However, it is interesting to examine the eigenmodes that live just above and below the band gap since these modes provides an intuitive understanding of the band gap origin. This Appendix provides a very brief example of these modes based on the atomic inspired sc photonic crystal introduced in Figure 3.3 with a band gap between the fifth and sixth bands.

Figures E.1 and E.2 shows the norm of the fifth and sixth modes respectively, analyzed at the high symmetry point X in the sc lattice.

It is clearly seen that for the lower mode, the energies are concentrated in the center of the high dielectric region of the photonic crystal. And furthermore that the energy of the upper mode is concentrated about the interface between the high and low dielectric regions. This shows the physical origin of the band gap as presented in Section 2.1.3 and [Joannopoulos et al., 1995].

(a) Isosurface of the norm of the fifth mode with isovalue 80. The isosurface is colored according the x-coordinate and the sc photonic crystal is plotted such that grey refers to ϵ_2 .

(b) Sliceplot of the electric field magnitude within a single sc photonic crystal.

Figure E.1: Plots of the photonic crystal and the electric field magnitude in the fifth mode just below the photonic band gap. It is seen that the energy is concentrated in the center of the high dielectric regions.

(a) Isosurface of the norm of the sixth mode with isovalue 100. The isosurface is colored according the x-coordinate and the sc photonic crystal is plotted such that grey refers to ϵ_2 .

(b) Sliceplot of the electric field magnitude within a single sc photonic crystal.

Figure E.2: Plots of the photonic crystal and the electric field magnitude in the sixth mode just above the photonic band gap. It is seen that the energy is concentrated at the interface between the high and low dielectric regions.

Maple Script

This Maple script computes the 1st order FE element equations for the stabilized Maxwell's EVP.

```

1 > restart;
2 > with(LinearAlgebra):
3 > with(CodeGeneration):
4 For the problem of: Maxwell vectorial equations
5 M = int_Ve curl N curl N dVe
6 K = int_Ve N^T N dVe
7 Shape functions EDGE ELEMENTS.
8 > xc := dx/2: yc := dy/2: zc := dz/2:
9 > N[1] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dy/dz*(yc+dy/2-y)*(zc+dz/2-z):
10 > N[2] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dy/dz*(-yc+dy/2+y)*(zc+dz/2-z):
11 > N[3] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dy/dz*(yc+dy/2-y)*(-zc+dz/2+z):
12 > N[4] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dy/dz*(-yc+dy/2+y)*(-zc+dz/2+z):
13 > N[5] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dz*(zc+dz/2-z)*(xc+dx/2-x):
14 > N[6] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dz*(-zc+dz/2+z)*(xc+dx/2-x):
15 > N[7] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dz*(zc+dz/2-z)*(-xc+dx/2+x):
16 > N[8] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dz*(-zc+dz/2+z)*(-xc+dx/2+x):
17 > N[9] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dy*(xc+dx/2-x)*(yc+dy/2-y):
18 > N[10] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dy*(-xc+dx/2+x)*(yc+dy/2-y):
19 > N[11] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dy*(xc+dx/2-x)*(-yc+dy/2+y):
20 > N[12] := (x,y,z) -> 1/dx/dy*(-xc+dx/2+x)*(-yc+dy/2+y):
21 >
22 Shape functions SCALAR LAGRANGE ELEMENTS
23 > a := dx: b := dy: c := dz:
24 > Ns[1] := (x,y,z) -> (a-x)*(b-y)*(c-z)/(a*b*c):
25 > Ns[2] := (x,y,z) -> (a+x)*(b-y)*(c-z)/(a*b*c):
26 > Ns[3] := (x,y,z) -> (a+x)*(b+y)*(c-z)/(a*b*c):
27 > Ns[4] := (x,y,z) -> (a-x)*(b+y)*(c-z)/(a*b*c):
28 > Ns[5] := (x,y,z) -> (a-x)*(b-y)*(c+z)/(a*b*c):
29 > Ns[6] := (x,y,z) -> (a+x)*(b-y)*(c+z)/(a*b*c):
30 > Ns[7] := (x,y,z) -> (a+x)*(b+y)*(c+z)/(a*b*c):
31 > Ns[8] := (x,y,z) -> (a-x)*(b+y)*(c+z)/(a*b*c):
32 Shape function Matrix: CURL
33 > Nmat := <<N[1](x,y,z),0,0>|<N[2](x,y,z),0,0>|
34 > <N[3](x,y,z),0,0>|<N[4](x,y,z),0,0>|
35 > <0,N[5](x,y,z),0>|<0,N[6](x,y,z),0>|
36 > <0,N[7](x,y,z),0>|<0,N[8](x,y,z),0>|
37 > <0,0,N[9](x,y,z)>|<0,0,N[10](x,y,z)>
38 > |<0,0,N[11](x,y,z)>|<0,0,N[12](x,y,z)>>>:
39 Shape function Matrix: Grad
40 > Nsmat := <
41 > <Ns[1](x,y,z)>|<Ns[2](x,y,z)>|<Ns[3](x,y,z)>|<Ns[4](x,y,z)>|
42 > <Ns[5](x,y,z)>|<Ns[6](x,y,z)>|<Ns[7](x,y,z)>|<Ns[8](x,y,z)>>>:
43 The CurlMatrix - eg. strain-displ.
44 > CurlNmat := Matrix(3,12):
45 > for i from 1 by 1 to 12 do
46 >   CurlNmat[1,i] := diff(Nmat[3,i],y) - diff(Nmat[2,i],z);
47 >   CurlNmat[2,i] := diff(Nmat[1,i],z) - diff(Nmat[3,i],x);
48 >   CurlNmat[3,i] := diff(Nmat[2,i],x) - diff(Nmat[1,i],y);
49 > end do:
50 The GradMatrix - eg. the scalar field
51 > GradMat := Matrix(3,8):
52 > for i from 1 by 1 to 8 do
53 >   GradMat[1,i] := diff(Nsmat[1,i],x);
54 >   GradMat[2,i] := diff(Nsmat[1,i],y);
55 >   GradMat[3,i] := diff(Nsmat[1,i],z);
56 > end do:
57 The coupling matrix:

```

```
58 > Btest := Transpose(Nmat) . GradMat:
59 > Be:=map(simplify, map(int, map(int, map(int, Btest, x=0..dx)
60 > , y=0..dy), z=0..dz)):
61 The M-matrix
62 > Mtest := Transpose(Nmat) . Nmat:
63 > Me:=map(simplify, map(int, map(int, map(int, Mtest, x=0..dx)
64 > , y=0..dy), z=0..dz)):
65 The K-matrix
66 > Ktest := Transpose(CurlNmat) . CurlNmat:
67 > Ke:=map(simplify, map(int, map(int, map(int, Ktest, x=0..dx)
68 > , y=0..dy), z=0..dz)):
69 Dump to Matlab/Fortran
70 > Matlab(Me, resultname = "Me"):
71 > Matlab(Ke, resultname = "Ke"):
72 > Matlab(Be, resultname = "Be"):
```

Content of the CD

This Appendix provides a table of contents for the CD accompanying the thesis.

```
3D_Design_Matlab_Figures/Chapter_5
                        /Chapter_6
OptimizationCode/DiamondOpt
                  /scOpt
```

The first folder contain Matlab figure files of the optimized designs presented in Chapter 5 and 6.

The second folder contain the COMSOL implementation of the optimization program. The optimization code can be executed on any platform with COMSOL 3.3a and Matlab 7.3 installed. The program is started by entering the desired folder and running the script `main.m`. If parallelization is possible, i.e. Linux machine with more than one CPU and COMSOL/MATLAB license, the script `scriptmulti.sh` is to be called from a terminal window¹. Due to copyright issues the MMA optimizer is not included. So before running the optimization program, the files `mmasub.m` and `subsolv.m` by K. Svanberg must be placed in each of the two optimization program folders.

Due to time issues the code has not been organized in a user-friendly fashion, and therefore the two optimization problems have been set up such that they solve the following problems:

Diamondopt: Solves the diamond optimization problem with dielectric spheres as initial guess.

scOpt: Solves the sc problem for gap 5-6 with the overlapping air sphere as initial guess

¹This files starts up 7 slave CPUs.


```

15     'k3', num2str(kvec(3));
16
17 % Reset fem.sol to hold gamma field as init var
18 fem.sol = asseminit(fem, 'init', initvec);
19
20 % Extend mesh
21 fem.xmesh = meshextend(fem, 'report', 'off');
22
23 % Solve problem
24 fem.sol = femeig(fem, ...
25     'conjugate', 'on', ...
26     'solcomp', {'psi', 'tExEyEz10'}, ...
27     'outcomp', {'psi', 'tExEyEz10', 'tFxFyFz10', 'gamma'}, ...
28     'U', fem.sol.u, ...
29     'neigs', neig, ...
30     'shift', 0.1, ...
31     'linsolver', 'pardiso', 'report', 'off');
32
33 % Control correct number of ev's are found
34 if length(fem.sol.lambda) < neig
35     fem.sol = femeig(fem, ...
36         'conjugate', 'on', ...
37         'solcomp', {'psi', 'tExEyEz10'}, ...
38         'outcomp', {'psi', 'tExEyEz10', 'tFxFyFz10', 'gamma'}, ...
39         'U', fem.sol.u, ...
40         'neigs', neig, ...
41         'shift', 0.1, ...
42         'krylovdim', floor(4*neig), ...
43         'linsolver', 'pardiso', 'report', 'off');
44 end
45
46 for i = 1:neig
47     eigen(i) = sqrt(real(fem.sol.lambda(i)));
48     eigVec(:, i) = fem.sol.u(:, i);
49 end
50 % end
51 resultCell = {eigen, eigVec};
    
```

H.3 Compute Objective, Constrains and Sensitivities

```

1 function [fem, f0val, fval, df0dx, dwdx, index] = SolveSens(fem, fem1, fem2, eigen, eigVec, ...
2     ia, iE, iF, ngap, SymMatCS, iter, index)
3
4 % Make vectors of upper eigvals
5 k = 0;
6 for i = ngap+1:size(eigen,1)
7     eigenUpper(1+k*size(eigen,2):(k+1)*size(eigen,2)) = eigen(i,:);
8     kvecUpper(1+k*size(eigen,2):(k+1)*size(eigen,2)) = 1:size(eigen,2);
9     IndexUpper(1+k*size(eigen,2):(k+1)*size(eigen,2)) = i;
10    k = k + 1;
11 end
12
13 [eigenUpper, SortUpper] = sort(eigenUpper, 'ascend');
14 kvecUpper = kvecUpper(SortUpper);
15 IndexUpper = IndexUpper(SortUpper);
16
17 % Make vector of lower eigvals
18 k = 0;
19 for i = 1:ngap
20     eigenLower(1+k*size(eigen,2):(k+1)*size(eigen,2)) = eigen(i,:);
21     kvecLower(1+k*size(eigen,2):(k+1)*size(eigen,2)) = 1:size(eigen,2);
22     IndexLower(1+k*size(eigen,2):(k+1)*size(eigen,2)) = i;
23    k = k + 1;
24 end
25
26 [eigenLower, SortLower] = sort(eigenLower, 'descend');
27 kvecLower = kvecLower(SortLower);
28 IndexLower = IndexLower(SortLower);
29
30 % find N
31 N = 5;
32 N = min(min(N, length(SortUpper)-1), length(SortLower)-1);
33
34 index.UpKvec = kvecUpper(1:N+1);
35 index.UpEig = IndexUpper(1:N+1);
36 index.LoKvec = kvecLower(1:N+1);
37 index.LoEig = IndexLower(1:N+1);
38 index.N = N+1;
39 N = N+1;
    
```

```

40
41 %% OBJECTIVE AND CONSTRAINTS
42 min_w_j_1 = eigen(index.UpEig(1),index.UpKvec(1));
43 max_w_j = eigen(index.LoEig(1),index.LoKvec(1));
44
45 % Compute f0val, -1* to switch from max to min
46 f0val = -1*2*(min_w_j_1 - max_w_j)/(min_w_j_1 + max_w_j);
47
48 % Compute fval
49 for i = 1:index.N-1
50     % Upper
51     fval(i,1) = min_w_j_1 - eigen(index.UpEig(i+1),index.UpKvec(i+1));
52     % Lower
53     fval(i+index.N-1,1) = eigen(index.LoEig(i+1),index.LoKvec(i+1)) - max_w_j;
54 end
55
56 %% SENSITIVITIES: d/dx (omega_j)
57 % UPPER DFDX
58 for i = 1:index.N % number of dw's
59     % place the right solution into F var.
60     eigVec(iF,index.UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i)) = eigVec(iE,index.UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i
61     ));
62     % Stiffness
63     L1 = zeros(size(fem.sol.u,1),1);
64     % Mass
65     L2 = assemble(fem2,'U',eigVec(:,index.UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i)),'Out','L','Solcomp'
66     ,{'psi','tExEyEz10','tFxFyFz10','gamma'},'conjugate','on','report','off');
67     % Mass Normalization
68     L4 = real(postint(fem,'epsilon*(conj(Ex)*Ex+conj(Ey)*Ey+conj(Ez)*Ez)','U',eigVec(:,
69     index.UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i))));
70     % Sensitivities
71     dfUpper(:,i) = 1/2/eigen(index.UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i))*(L1(ia) - eigen(index.
72     UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i))^2*L2(ia))./L4;
73 end
74
75 % LOWER DFDX
76 for i = 1:index.N % number of dw's
77     % place the right solution into F var.
78     eigVec(iF,index.LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i)) = eigVec(iE,index.LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i
79     ));
80     % Stiffness
81     L1 = zeros(size(fem.sol.u,1),1);
82     % Mass
83     L2 = assemble(fem2,'U',eigVec(:,index.LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i)),'Out','L','Solcomp'
84     ,{'psi','tExEyEz10','tFxFyFz10','gamma'},'conjugate','on','report','off');
85     % Mass Normalization
86     L4 = real(postint(fem,'epsilon*(conj(Ex)*Ex+conj(Ey)*Ey+conj(Ez)*Ez)','U',eigVec(:,
87     index.LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i))));
88     % Sensitivities
89     dfLower(:,i) = 1/2/eigen(index.LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i))*(L1(ia) - eigen(index.
90     LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i))^2*L2(ia))./L4;
91 end
92
93 %% dfdzmat
94 % Index: ev, kv, x
95 dfdzmat = zeros(size(eigen,1),size(eigen,2),length(ia));
96
97 % fill in the blanks
98 for i = 1:length(index.UpEig)
99     dfdzmat(index.UpEig(i),index.UpKvec(i,:),:) = dfUpper(:,i);
100 end
101 for i = 1:length(index.LoEig)
102     dfdzmat(index.LoEig(i),index.LoKvec(i,:),:) = dfLower(:,i);
103 end
104
105 %% UPDATE MEW
106 [multi] = FindMultiEig(eigen,1e-5);
107
108 %% COMPUTE MULTIPLE EIG ANALYSIS and update dfdzmat
109 for j = 1:size(eigen,2)
110     i = 2; % skip the zero mode
111     % Find number of mev clusters
112     entry = nonzeros(unique(multi(:,j)));
113     for i = 1:length(entry)
114         % find indices for the ev's
115         ind = find(multi(:,j)==entry(i));
116         % make vector of mev and matrix of corresponding evectors
117         w = eigen(ind,j);
118         evv = eigVec(:,ind,j);
119         % Call routine to compute new sens c.f. Pedersen
120         [dw] = ComputeMEV(w,evv,ia,iE,iF,fem,fem1,fem2);

```

```

116     % Place new dw into dfdxmat
117     for h = 1:length(ind)
118         dfdxmat(ind(h),j,:) = dw(:,h);
119     end
120 end
121 end
122
123 %% SYMMETRIES
124 dfdxsymmat = zeros(size(eigen,1),size(eigen,2),size(SymMatCS,1));
125
126 for i = 1:size(eigen,1)
127     for j = 1:size(eigen,2)
128         for h = 1:size(SymMatCS,1)
129             dfdxsymmat(i,j,h) = sum(dfdxmat(i,j,nonzeros(SymMatCS(h,2:end))));
130         end
131     end
132 end
133 end
134 %% PUT SENS IN FORMAT FOR MMA
135 dfUmin(:,1) = dfdxsymmat(index.UpEig(1),index.UpKvec(1),:);
136 dfLmax(:,1) = dfdxsymmat(index.LoEig(1),index.LoKvec(1),:);
137
138
139 % Sensitivity of objective, -1* to switch from max to min
140 df0dx(:,1) = -1*4*( max_w_j*dfUmin - min_w_j_1*dfLmax )/( min_w_j_1 + max_w_j )^2;
141
142 % Sensitivity of constraints
143 for i = 1:index.N-1
144     dfU(:,1) = dfdxsymmat(index.UpEig(i+1),index.UpKvec(i+1),:);
145     dfL(:,1) = dfdxsymmat(index.LoEig(i+1),index.LoKvec(i+1),:);
146     dfdx(i,:) = dfUmin - dfU;
147     dfdx(i+index.N-1,:) = dfL - dfLmax;
148 end
149
150 if index.N == 0
151     dfdx = [];
152     fval = [];
153 end
154
155 return
156

```

Function to determine if there are multiple eigenvalues

```

1 function [multi] = FindMultiEig(evv,tol)
2 % evv: Matrix containing the eigenvalues w2: neig x size(kvec)
3 % tol: tolerance
4 % multi: matrix of integers. > 0 implies multiple ev's
5
6 ev = size(evv,1);
7 kv = size(evv,2);
8 multi=zeros(ev,kv);
9
10 % Find multiple eigens.
11 for j = 1:kv
12     k = 1;
13     i = 3; % Use that COMSOL returns a zero mode !
14     while i <= ev
15         if abs(evv(i,j) - evv(i-1,j)) < tol
16             multi(i,j) = k;
17             multi(i-1,j) = k;
18             for h=i+1:ev
19                 if abs(evv(h,j) - evv(h-1,j)) < tol
20                     multi(h,j) = k;
21                 else
22                     k = k+1;
23                     i = h-1;
24                     break
25                 end
26             end
27         end
28         i = i+1;
29     end
30 end
31
32 end

```

Function that computes the sensitivities corresponding to multiple eigenvalues as given in [Pedersen, 2006]

```

1 function [dw] = ComputeMEV(w,V,ia,iE,iF,fem,fem1,fem2)
2
3 % number of design variables (both active and symmetry redundant)
4 p = length(ia);
5 % number of MEV
6 n = length(w);
7 % V = R(mxn)
8 dw = zeros(p,n);
9
10
11 % normalize Eigenvectors:
12 for i = 1:n
13     V(iF,i) = V(iE,i);
14     L4 = real(postint(fem,'epsilon*(conj(Ex)*Ex+conj(Ey)*Ey+conj(Ez)*Ez)','U',V(:,i)));
15     V(:,i) = V(:,i) / sqrt(L4);
16 end
17
18 % setup Gdummy which contain all: D_i*(diff(K,x_e)-w^2*diff(M,x_e))*D_j
19 Gdummy = zeros(p,n*n);
20 c = 0;
21 for i = 1:n
22     for j = 1:n
23         c = c + 1;
24         V(iF,i) = V(iE,j);
25         L2 = assemble(fem2,'U',V(:,i),'Out','L','Solcomp',...
26             {'psi','tExEyEz10','tFxFyFz10','gamma'},'conjugate','on','report','off');
27         Gdummy(:,c) = -1*w(1)^2*L2(ia);
28     end
29 end
30
31 % Build dw:
32 for e = 1:p
33     % Setup Gmat
34     Gmat = zeros(n,n);
35     c = 0;
36     for i = 1:n
37         for j = 1:n
38             c = c + 1;
39             Gmat(i,j) = Gdummy(e,c);
40         end
41     end
42     % solve evp and put into dw
43     E = eig(Gmat);
44     dw(e,:) = real(E);
45 end
46 % update lambdas to freqs.
47 dw = 1/2/w(1)*dw;

```

H.4 Plotting Tools

```

1 % Plotting routines for design visualization
2
3 % Matlab isosurface plot
4 edgecolor = 'none';
5 facecolor = [0.85 0.85 0.85];
6 isoVal = 0.9;
7
8 figure(1)
9 % xiso contains the full design in Matlab numbering, i.e.
10 % a 3D array in (y,x,z)
11 % Smooth design
12 xiso = smooth3(xiso,'box',1);
13 % isosurface
14 p1 = patch(isosurface(xiso,isoVal),...
15     'FaceColor','blue','EdgeColor',edgecolor);
16 % Close end faces
17 p2 = patch(isocaps(xiso,isoVal),...
18     'FaceColor',facecolor,'EdgeColor',edgecolor);
19 view(3); axis vis3d tight
20 axis off
21 camlight; lighting phong
22
23 % Comsol element plot
24 figure(2)
25 postplot(fem,'tetdata','1-gamma','ellogic','(gamma>0.5)','tetdlim',[0 1],...
26     'tetmap',[linspace(1,0.3,64)*0 linspace(1,0.3,64)*1 linspace(1,0.3,64)*0])
27 view(3);
28 light('Position',[-0.6 -0.8 0.8],'style','infinite');

```

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